

Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan

Faculty of Agriculture

Department of Plant Protection

Study on taxonomy of *Brenneria* genus in Iran

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Doctor of
Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Plant Pathology**

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**Dedicated to my dear father, mother,
and sister**

Acknowledgments

I am grateful beyond words, beyond my own understanding, beyond the time I have, and even beyond my existence. O Lord, I thank You, for You alone have seen me, You alone have called me—in the darkness of night, in the cold silence of time, and amid the clamor of the world—You alone have been my companion, my helper, and my guide.

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"Before I draw my final breath,
Before the curtain falls,
Before the last flower wilts,
I intend to live,
I intend to love,
I intend to be.
In this darkened world,
In this era filled with tragedies,
In this realm of bitterness,
Among those who need me,
Those I need,
Those worthy of praise,
To discover,
To marvel,
To recognize anew—
Who am I?
Who can I be?

Who do I wish to be?
So that days do not pass in vain,
So that hours gain life,
So that moments become precious,
When I laugh,
When I weep,
When I fall silent,
On my journey toward You,
Toward myself,
Toward God—
A path unknown,
Thorny,
Uneven,
A path I step upon,
Have stepped upon,
With no thought of turning back..."

— Margot Bickel

Abstract

The cultivation of Persian walnut (*Juglans regia*) in Iran is concentrated in the mountainous regions of Zagros and Alborz, encompassing the provinces of Mazandaran, Golestan, Semnan, Kurdistan, Hamedan, Lorestan, Isfahan, Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Fars and Kerman. Due to the widespread distribution of walnut across Iran, these areas are prone to the spread of chronic bacterial diseases, including shallow bark canker caused by *Brenneria nigrifluens*. These walnut-growing regions in Iran are also characterized by abundant oak vegetation. However, due to environmental stresses especially drought, the oak population in these areas is declining, leading to climatic changes which in turn increase the risk of diseases caused by emerging and invasive pathogenic agents or host jumping of existing pathogens. Moreover, some of these regions, especially in the central provinces, are located in remote and inaccessible areas or rural villages and less frequented passages, for which disease occurrence has been less documented. Therefore, better understanding the distribution and association of pathogenic bacteria is important, which itself requires accurate identification of these agents. To investigate the footprint of this disease in the mentioned regions, 42 available bacterial strains in the bacterial culture collection at Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan that were collected from these areas were used. Biochemical and pathogenicity tests and molecular analyses of these isolates revealed that *B. nigrifluens* is the main causal agent of shallow bark canker in these provinces and has been reported as the dominant pathogenic bacterium of bacterial canker disease over the years, whose genetic diversity has been studied by other researchers. Now, with the aim of evaluating factors associated with bacterial canker in walnut and oak trees in remote walnut orchards and oak forests in central Iran, sampling was performed and 80 bacterial isolates were collected from 84 symptomatic walnut trees and 16 symptomatic oak trees. Twenty-one isolates after positive reactions in the hypersensitivity and pathogenicity tests were selected for further analysis. These isolates were classified into two groups of “*B. nigrifluens*” and “*Brenneria*-like” based on biochemical similarities to the standard strain (*B. nigrifluens* ICMP 20120) and using species-specific primers (F1/C3). The “*Brenneria*-like” group showed different biochemical characteristics compared to the “*B. nigrifluens*” group. Multilocus sequence analysis using *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB* and *atpD* genes revealed that isolates of the “*B. nigrifluens*” group belonged to this species, while isolates of the “*Brenneria*-like” group belonged to *Gibbsiella quercinecans*.

Keywords: Multilocus sequence analysis, Bacterial canker, Walnut, *Brenneria nigrifluens*, *Gibbsiella quercinecans*

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Chapter One

Introduction

1-1 Walnut and Its Importance

Walnuts belong to the family *Juglandaceae* and the genus *Juglans*. This family comprises approximately 10 genera and 60 species, primarily distributed across the Northern Hemisphere. The genus *Juglans* includes 21 species, ranging from southeastern Europe to Japan. Walnuts are valued for their edible kernels and are widely cultivated. Furthermore, various parts of the walnut tree and fruit contain valuable compounds utilized across multiple industries. For instance, the green husk of the walnut fruit is rich in antioxidant and phenolic compounds, making it a natural and healthy additive in the food and pharmaceutical industries. The hard shell of the walnut contains significant amounts of lignin and tannin, which are used in the production of dyes and insulating materials. Additionally, the thin skin of the walnut kernel is a potent source of antioxidants, finding extensive applications in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical sectors. Beyond these, the bark, roots, branches, and leaves of the walnut tree also contain bioactive compounds with potential uses in industries such as pharmaceuticals and chemicals.

Notable walnut species include *Juglans mandshurica* Maxim., native to northeastern Asia, where its green husk is employed in traditional medicine; *Juglans nigra*, native to northeastern America; and *Juglans regia* L., native to Europe, Asia, and the eastern and southern United States, which is commercially cultivated for both its timber and edible kernels. The Persian walnut, or *Juglans regia* L., is a significant and versatile crop grown commercially worldwide, including in Iran, and is prized for its nutritional and medicinal properties (Jahanban-Esfahlan et al., 2019). According to data from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAOSTAT) in 2021, Iran ranks as the third-largest walnut producer globally and the second-largest in Asia, following China (see Figures 1-1 and 1-2). Based on these statistics, Iran's walnut production in 2021 reached 386,976 tons (see Table 1-1).

Figure 1-1 Walnut-Producing Countries Worldwide

Figure 1-2 Percentage Distribution of Global Walnut Producers by Continent (FAO, 2021)

Table 1-1 Leading Walnut-Producing Countries (FAO, 2021)

Rank	Country	Production (Tons)	Rank	Country	Production (Tons)
1	China	1,100,000	28	Poland	6,800
2	United States	657,710	29	Brazil	6,215
3	Iran	386,976	30	Kyrgyzstan	6,110
4	Turkey	325,000	31	Hungary	5,950
5	Chile	148,000	32	Australia	5,020
6	Burkina Faso	137,267	33	Bulgaria	4,730
7	Mexico	135,946	34	North Macedonia	4,667
8	Ukraine	115,420	35	Bosnia and Herzegovina	4,340
9	Greece	62,810	36	Armenia	4,222
10	Romania	54,250	37	Lebanon	3,926
11	Uzbekistan	47,480	38	Kazakhstan	3,166
12	France	37,740	39	Austria	2,750
13	Morocco	25,065	40	Switzerland	1,923
14	Egypt	24,029	41	Iraq	1,505
15	Argentina	21,582	42	South Korea	1,156
16	Spain	18,880	43	Montenegro	722
17	Maldives	18,400	44	New Zealand	700
18	Belarus	16,525	45	Slovenia	590
19	Pakistan	15,369	46	Peru	258

Rank	Country	Production (Tons)	Rank	Country	Production (Tons)
20	Afghanistan	14,743	47	Czech Republic	180
21	Italy	14,660	48	Bhutan	178
22	Azerbaijan	13,136	49	Croatia	170
23	Syria	11,990	50	Palestine	158
24	Nepal	9,054	51	Cyprus	140
25	Serbia	7,646	52	Lithuania	140
26	Portugal	7,540	53	Luxembourg	20
27	Georgia	7,200	54	Jordan	8

1-2 Oak and Its Importance

The oak tree is one of the most significant forest trees in Iran. Various oak species are found in the northern and western forests of the country, with the Persian oak, scientifically named *Quercus brantii*, constituting over 50% of the Zagros Forest area (see Figure 1-3). In botanical classification, this tree falls within the class *Angiosperm*, subclass *Eudicots*, infraclass *Rosids*, order *Fagales*, family *Fagaceae*, and genus *Quercus*. Oaks are distributed across the Northern Hemisphere, spanning Asia, North America, Europe, and Africa. Approximately 200–245 oak species exist in America, while Eurasia hosts 196 species, with Europe having only 22. Asia boasts over 100 species, exhibiting significant diversity in China and Vietnam (Axelrod, 1983). In East Asia, oak species extend from Manchuria to Myanmar and Thailand, predominantly thriving in mountainous regions. Key species in this area include *Q. semecarpifolia*, *Q. lanata*, *Q. kingiana*, *Q. griffithii*, and *Q. acutissima*. In Central Asia, oaks range from central China to the western Himalayas, encompassing Bhutan, Nepal, northern Pakistan, and Afghanistan. Species such as *Q. baloot* and *Q. dilatata* are found in the western Himalayas, while *Q. semecarpifolia* grows at high altitudes in Nepal (Negi and Naithani, 1995).

Figure 1-3 Distribution of Various Oak Species Across Different Regions of the World Based on Denk et al. (2017)

Oaks possess numerous chemical compounds with proven therapeutic properties. Tannins in the bark and leaves of oaks exhibit antiseptic and wound-healing effects. Furthermore, oak extracts demonstrate anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antitussive, and diuretic properties, making them valuable in treating skin conditions, indigestion, anemia, rickets, and tuberculosis. Oak wood is also utilized as fuel and in crafting implements. As a vital natural resource, oak plays a significant role in Iran's traditional medicine, underscoring the importance of conserving its reserves (Bahmani et al., 2015).

1-3 Bacterial Diseases of Walnut and Oak

Bacterial blight of walnut is one of the most significant and widespread bacterial diseases affecting walnut trees, caused by the bacterium *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *juglandis* (Pierce, 1901; Vauterin et al., 1995). This disease manifests as brown-to-black spots on leaves, stems, and walnut kernels, leading to premature fruit drop, kernel shriveling, and darkening. Bacterial blight has been reported globally, including in European, Asian, North and South American, Oceanian countries, and Iran. It spreads through rain and insects, overwintering in infected buds and branches, making it the most critical bacterial disease of walnut worldwide. Recently, a new bacterial blight disease affecting walnut leaves and fruits has been observed, characterized by necrosis and exudation on leaves, caused by the newly identified species *Xanthomonas euroxanthea* (Martins et al., 2020).

Superficial bark canker of walnut is another disease, induced by the bacterium *Brenneria nigrifluens* (Wilson et al., 1957). It causes vertical cracks on the trunk and main branches, as well as circular brown-to-black spots beneath the bark surface. These irregular, scattered spots exude a blackish sap. Superficial bark canker is confined to the outer bark layer and is commonly observed in commercial cultivars. Its spread is less dependent on temperature or tree age and has been documented in Iran, European countries, and the United States (Frutose, 2010).

Deep bark canker of walnut, caused by *Brenneria rubrifaciens* (Wilson et al., 1967), results in wide fissures and deep cavities in the trunk and primary branches, from which a reddish-brown fluid ooze. These cankers penetrate the vascular layers and cambium, weakening branches, reducing yield, and potentially causing tree death. This disease predominantly affects trees older than 15 years, accompanied by a gradual decline in growth and productivity. The *Hartley* cultivar is particularly susceptible to deep bark canker. Environmental stressors, such as water deficiency, exacerbate symptoms, and the disease is more prevalent at higher temperatures (Frutose, 2010).

While bacterial blight is recognized as the most significant bacterial disease of walnut globally, superficial and deep bark cankers also cause considerable damage in certain regions, including Iran, with increasing reports and spread over time. Additionally, the bacterium *Gibbsiella quercinecans* has recently been identified in Iran as a causative agent of bacterial canker in walnut (Allahverdi-pour et al., 2020).

Oak leaf scorch, caused by the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*, results in brown or orange spots on leaves (Desprez-Loustau et al., 2021). Primarily transmitted by insects such as *Philaenus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris*, this disease is predominantly found along the eastern coast of the United States. The bacterium resides in the leaf veins, obstructing sap flow and causing leaf wilting (Godefroid and Duran, 2022).

Acute oak decline, triggered by the bacteria *G. quercinecans*, *Rahnella victoriana*, and *Brenneria goodwinii*, is characterized by thick exudates seeping from bark fissures. These gram-negative bacteria, recently identified, contribute to necrotic lesions beneath the bark, leading to rapid tree weakening and death within 5–6 years (Brady et al., 2010; Denman et al., 2014; Denman et al., 2017; Bakhshi Ganje et al., 2020; Brady et al., 2022).

Drippy Nut disease of oak, caused by *Brenneria quercina* (previously classified as *Erwinia quercina*), results in clear, brown, or frothy exudates from oak fruits (Hildebrand and Schroth, 1967). Symptoms intensify in spring and autumn, with the bacterium likely entering the fruit via damage caused by insects of the *Curculionidae* family. Recently, the negative impact of *B. goodwinii* on the oak species *Q. brantii* has been reported in Iran (Bakhshi Ganje et al., 2020). Research by Zolfaghari et al. (2022) highlights that drought, extreme temperatures, and water scarcity stress plants, increasing their susceptibility to diseases and contributing to the widespread decline of oak trees in Iran in recent years.

1-4 Importance of Phylogenetics, Method Selection, and Modeling

Phylogenetics, taxonomy, or the scientific classification of living organisms, is a cornerstone of biological sciences, particularly plant pathology. Without precise identification and classification of pathogens, studying and controlling plant diseases becomes unfeasible. Descriptive taxonomy involves the identification, diagnosis, naming, and scientific classification of various pathogenic species, including bacteria, fungi, viruses, and nematodes. Given the high genetic and morphological diversity among pathogens, descriptive taxonomy plays a crucial role in distinguishing between species and subspecies. Neglecting this diversity can lead to misidentification of disease agents and the adoption of inappropriate control measures. Moreover, taxonomy serves as a foundational science for population genetics and evolutionary studies of pathogens, making proficiency in its principles essential for plant pathologists conducting advanced research in this field.

Reduced focus and investment in descriptive taxonomy, a shortage of specialists in fungal and bacterial pathogen taxonomy, and the widespread use of outdated rather than precise scientific names are among the primary challenges facing taxonomy in plant pathology. Additionally, rapid advancements in molecular and genetic techniques have fundamentally altered the classification and nomenclature of key pathogens, necessitating continuous updates and revisions to taxonomic knowledge among plant pathology experts. This underscores the need for comprehensive collaboration among taxonomists, geneticists, and plant pathologists (Crous, 2005).

The selection of appropriate phylogenetic methods is critical for accurate analysis. Researchers have proposed various approaches to predict or approximate species phylogenies, each with its strengths and limitations. For instance, the maximum likelihood method, widely recommended and applied, relies on identifying parameters that maximize similarity within the studied data. However, its use with large, complex datasets requires powerful processors and is time-consuming, though it remains one of the most utilized methods across studies. In contrast, the maximum parsimony method seeks the simplest tree to explain the data, rooted in the principle of *Occam's Razor*¹ or the "Principle of Simplicity in Explanation" (Kannan and Wheeler, 2012). Another prevalent approach, Bayesian analysis, offers specific advantages: it avoids overfitting in small samples, unlike maximum likelihood, and does not require exhaustive parameter computation for posterior probability estimation, though it is computationally slower.

Equally important is the selection of an appropriate model for phylogenetic data analysis. Evolutionary models provide assumptions about nucleotide substitution processes and must accurately reflect the data generation process to prevent erroneous inferences. These models account for base frequencies, substitution rates, and rate variation. While the goal is not to perfectly simulate evolution but to provide a useful approximation, overly complex models may improve fit but risk overfitting. Thus, assessing

¹ *The Occam's Razor* (in English: Occam's razor) is a principle attributed to William of Ockham, an English logician and philosopher of the 14th century. William of Ockham proposed a concept that became widely known as *Occam's Razor*, "Ockham's Razor," the "Principle of Parsimony," or the "Principle of Simplicity in Explanation." According to this principle, when two different explanations are offered for the cause of a phenomenon, the more complex explanation is more likely to contain errors. Therefore, under equal conditions, the simpler explanation is more likely to be correct.

model fit with real data using criteria such as likelihood is essential. Fit refers to how well a model aligns with observed data, with better fit indicating a more accurate representation of data patterns (Posada, 2003; Ward, 2008).

1-5 Research Objectives

In recent years, walnut diseases have become increasingly prevalent across most provinces of Iran, posing a serious threat to members of the *Juglandaceae* family and other forest trees under favorable conditions. Currently, no effective control measures exist for bark canker, decline, or related symptoms. Prevention and control hinge on accurately identifying the disease-causing agents, making precise pathogen identification the first step toward implementing suitable strategies.

Globally, reports have emerged of bacterial cankers caused by genera or species previously unrecognized as pathogens, as well as expanded host ranges of known bacterial species, necessitating further investigation of bacterial agents in Iran's orchard and forest regions. Moreover, no studies in Iran have yet explored host-switching of bacterial pathogens between cultivated and forest plants. Given Iran's vast climatic diversity and extensive range of orchard and forest products, comprehensive data on the species responsible for these destructive plant diseases are imperative.

This research aims to investigate the primary bacterial agents involved in walnut and oak canker in central Iran, assess their pathogenicity on these two plant hosts, and determine their precise taxonomic positions using multi-locus sequence analysis of housekeeping genes, alongside biochemical characterization.

Chapter Two

Research Background

2-1 Bacterial Canker of Walnut

Walnut trees are increasingly susceptible to bacterial diseases that severely damage the trunk, branches, and even immature fruit (Golmohammadi et al., 2002; Gonzalez et al., 2002; Martins et al., 2020). Among the most significant of these diseases is bacterial canker, classified into deep bark canker (DBC) and shallow bark canker (SBC), caused by *Brenneria rubrifaciens* and *B. nigrifluens*, respectively. These pathogens have a considerable impact on the walnut production and timber industries (Illicic et al., 2021). Bacterial canker of walnut was first reported in California, USA, by Wilson et al. (1957) and has since been documented in various regions worldwide (Rahimian, 1989; Lopez et al., 1994; Morone et al., 1998; Menard et al., 2004; Yousefikopaei et al., 2007; Soylu et al., 2021). The genus *Brenneria* was described by Hauben et al. (1998) to reclassify six bacterial species previously placed in the genus *Erwinia* (Gonzalez et al., 2002). These species include *B. alni*, *B. nigrifluens*, *B. paradisiaca*, *B. quercina*, *B. rubrifaciens*, and *B. salicis*, with *B. nigrifluens* and *B. rubrifaciens* being the most extensively studied (see Table 2-1).

Key countries reporting bacterial canker of walnut include Iran (Yousefikopaei et al., 2007; Jamalzade et al., 2012; Roshangar and Harighi, 2009), France, Spain (Loreti et al., 2008), Italy (Loreti et al., 2005; Pardatscher and Schweigkofler, 2009), and the United States (Wilson et al., 1957).

Table 2-1 Earliest Reports of Bacterial Canker on Walnut Trees Caused by *Brenneria* Isolates

Region	Host	Pathogen	Identification Method	Source
California	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	<i>Erwinia nigrifluens</i>	Symptoms, Biochemical Tests	Wilson et al., 1957
California	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>Brenneria rubrifaciens</i> , <i>E. nigrifluens</i>	Symptoms and Signs	Schaad and Wilson, 1971
Iran	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	Biochemical Characterization	Rahimian, 1989
Spain	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	Biochemical Characterization	Lopez et al., 1994
Italy	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>E. nigrifluens</i>	Biochemical Characterization	Morone et al., 1998
Europe	<i>Juglans hindsii</i>	<i>B. rubrifaciens</i>	Biochemical Characterization, ELISA, Pathogenicity Test	Gonzalez et al., 2002
France	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	Biochemical and Pathogenicity Tests	Menard et al., 2004

Region	Host	Pathogen	Identification Method	Source
Iran	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	16S rRNA Sequencing	Roshangar and Harighi, 2009
Serbia	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	16S rRNA and <i>gyrB</i> Sequencing	Popovic et al., 2009
Hungary	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	Symptoms, Biochemical Characterization, 16S rRNA Sequencing	Vegh et al., 2014
Turkey	<i>J. regia</i> L.	<i>B. nigrifluens</i>	Symptoms, Pathogenicity, MALDI-TOF, 16S rRNA and <i>gyrB</i> Sequencing	Soylu et al., 2021

2-2 Classification of the Genus *Brenneria*

2-2-1 The 16S rRNA Gene: Origins, Advantages, and Challenges

The initial classification of the genus *Brenneria* was conducted by Hauben et al. (1998), based on a study of the 16S rRNA region among pathogenic bacterial isolates from the genera *Erwinia*, *Pantoea*, and *Enterobacter*, compared with other known members of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family at that time. In this study, the species *Erwinia alni*, *E. nigrifluens*, *E. paradisiaca*, *E. quercina*, *E. rubrifaciens*, and *E. salicis* were reclassified into a new genus named *Brenneria*, as *B. alni*, *B. nigrifluens*, *B. paradisiaca*, *B. quercina*, *B. rubrifaciens*, and *B. salicis*, respectively (see Figure 2-1).

The 16S rRNA gene is the most commonly used genetic marker in bacterial phylogenetic and taxonomic studies due to its ubiquitous presence in bacteria, relatively stable function over time, and suitable length for analysis (approximately 1,500 base pairs). However, it has limitations. For example, the standard strains *Bacillus globisporus* and *B. psychrophilus* exhibit over 99.5% similarity in their 16S rRNA sequences, yet DNA-DNA hybridization studies reveal only 23–50% similarity between them (Fox et al., 1992). Sequencing of 16S rRNA targets specific variable regions, with differing sensitivity for distinguishing related taxa, leading to discrepancies in results and taxonomic interpretations that complicate studies (Yang et al., 2016). Additionally, this gene has limited ability to differentiate closely related species or bacterial isolates at the subspecies level. While 16S rRNA sequencing is a valuable tool for bacterial classification and identification, its results come with inherent constraints. To address these challenges, researchers have turned to sequencing housekeeping genes, which are conserved across bacterial species and offer greater utility for taxonomic studies at the species or subspecies level.

2-2-2 Housekeeping Genes

Housekeeping genes used in studies of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family include *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD*. The *gyrB* gene encodes the B subunit of bacterial DNA gyrase, a type II topoisomerase that introduces negative supercoils into DNA molecules, playing a critical role in DNA replication and transcription in prokaryotes. It has been widely used as a taxonomic marker in bacterial phylogenetics and is now considered a near-standard for preliminary identification. The *gyrB* gene evolves more rapidly than 16S rRNA and is rarely transferred horizontally between species, with most bacteria possessing a single copy. However, some *Streptomyces* species have two distinct *gyrB* copies, one conferring resistance to the antibiotic novobiocin. Its essential role in DNA topology management and

sequence variability makes *gyrB* an ideal target for assessing evolutionary relationships among bacterial taxa (Kasai et al., 1998).

The *rpoB* gene encodes the beta subunit of RNA polymerase and is a key candidate for phylogenetic analysis and bacterial identification, particularly for closely related isolates. Alongside 16S rRNA, *rpoB* has aided in defining new bacterial species, optimizing bacterial community analysis, and monitoring rifampin resistance mutations. Its near-universal presence in bacteria makes its sequence inclusion valuable for describing new species (Adekambi et al., 2009).

The *atpD* gene, encoding the beta subunit of ATP synthase, is suitable for phylogenetic analysis due to its widespread distribution, functional stability, and conserved sequence. Phylogenetic relationships based on *atpD* sequence comparisons closely resemble those derived from 16S rRNA, with the gene playing a role in ATP synthesis from ADP (Christensen and Olsen, 1998).

The *infB* gene encodes the translation initiation factor in prokaryotes. A portion of this gene, coding for the GTP-binding domain of initiation factor 2 (IF2), has demonstrated sufficient variability to serve as a phylogenetic marker in prokaryotes, particularly within the *Enterobacteriaceae* family (Hedegaard et al., 1999).

Figure 2-1 Phylogenetic Tree Proposed for the *Enterobacteriaceae* Family Based on 16S rRNA Sequence Comparison by Hauben et al. (1998)

Building on this, Brady et al. (2012) refined the taxonomic status of the genus *Brenneria* and improved the classification of *Brenneria quercina* using multi-locus sequence analysis (MLSA) based on the housekeeping genes *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD*. The results indicated that *Brenneria* species split into two distinct groups. The first group, forming the *Brenneria* cluster, includes *B. salicis*, *B. alni*, *B. nigrifluens*, and *B. rubrifaciens*. Within this cluster, *B. nigrifluens* aligns with *B. salicis*, *B. alni*, and *B. rubrifaciens*. The second group comprises *B. quercina* and new oak isolates, reclassified as a new genus and species, *Lonsdalea quercina*. Thus, MLSA confirmed *B. nigrifluens* as a core member of the *Brenneria* genus, alongside *B. salicis*, *B. alni*, and *B. rubrifaciens*, solidifying their taxonomic positions as primary species within the genus (see Figure 2-2).

Figure 2-2 Phylogenetic Tree Proposed by Brady et al. (2012) for the Genus *Brenneria* Based on MLSA Using *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* Sequence Comparisons.

Bacterial canker is easily recognizable by its primary symptoms, including irregular shapes on the trunk and branches, and sticky brown-to-black exudates from vertical fissures, particularly near the tree crown. Severe decline due to bacterial canker can lead to tree death within 4–6 years (Moretti and Buonauro, 2010; Tkaczyk et al., 2021; Tenorio-Baigorria et al., 2022). Hildebrand and Schroth (1967) identified *Erwinia quercina* as the causative agent of Drippy nut disease in oak trees in California's central and northern valleys. This bacterium, reclassified as *B. quercina* by Hauben et al. (1998), was

isolated from dripping acorn exudates, with symptoms confined to the acorns and absent from other oak tree parts. *B. quercina* was first observed on oak species exhibiting bark canker symptoms in several central Spanish forests (Biosca et al., 2003). A separate study by Poza-Carrión et al. (2008) identified a “*Serratia*-like” group as responsible for similar symptoms. Subsequent analysis linked these isolates to bacterial isolates from oak trees with widespread stem bleeding symptoms, confirming their classification as a new genus and species, *Gibbsiella quercinecans* (Brady et al., 2010).

The genus *Gibbsiella* was described by Brady et al. (2010) and named in honor of British plant pathologist John N. Gibbs for his contributions to forest tree pathology. It is gram-negative, facultatively anaerobic, oxidase-negative, and catalase-positive. Cells occur singly, in pairs, or in tetrads, lacking flagella. Colonies on nutrient agar appear white to cream-colored, round, convex, and with smooth margins. Isolates can grow at temperatures between 10 and 40°C. The type species, *G. quercinecans*, was isolated from oak trees affected by acute oak decline in Britain and Spain. *G. quercinecans* is consistently isolated from damaged tissues of oak trees with acute oak decline in Britain. Primary symptoms include sticky, dark exudates from vertical bark fissures, necrotic underlying tissues, and regular larval galleries of the insect *Agrilus biguttatus*.

In Brady et al. (2010), the taxonomic status of *G. quercinecans* was detailed as follows: Isolates from oak trees with decline in Britain and Spain were initially examined via 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Results showed high sequence similarity (98.2–99.7%) among isolates, forming a distinct cluster in the phylogenetic tree based on this gene. To confirm genetic relatedness, the housekeeping genes *gyrB* and *rpoB* were sequenced, and corresponding phylogenetic trees were constructed (see Figure 2-3). These isolates formed distinct clusters, corroborated by DNA-DNA hybridization tests showing high DNA similarity (78–93%) among them. Phenotypic tests and cellular fatty acid profiling further distinguished these isolates from other *Enterobacteriaceae* members. Based on these findings, the isolates were designated as a new species within the novel genus *Gibbsiella*.

Figure 2-3 Phylogenetic Tree Proposed by Brady et al. (2010) for *Gibbsiella quercinecans* Based on *gyrB* Sequence Analysis

Following the initial description of *G. quercinecans*, additional species and subspecies of this genus have been isolated and characterized from affected oak trees. However, *G. quercinecans* remains the predominant species associated with acute oak decline in Britain (Brady et al., 2014; Brady et al., 2015). Other species of this genus have also been linked to oak decline and isolated from declining black oak trees in southern California (Brady et al., 2014). *G. quercinecans* is not considered a primary pathogen in oak trees but likely acts as an opportunistic secondary infection in pre-damaged tissues, potentially exacerbating disease symptoms (Brady et al., 2010).

In Brady et al. (2014), the description of the genus *Gibbsiella* was refined. Twelve bacterial isolates from a black oak tree exhibiting decline symptoms in California were analyzed. MLSA using the housekeeping genes *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* showed these isolates forming a distinct cluster alongside other *Gibbsiella* members in the phylogenetic tree. Sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene from two representative isolates confirmed their divergence from known *Gibbsiella* species. DNA-DNA hybridization revealed low DNA similarity with other *Gibbsiella* species, indicating a new taxon. Phenotypic tests and cellular fatty acid profiles further highlighted differences from other genus members. Consequently, these isolates were proposed as a new species, *G. greigii*, within *Gibbsiella*.

Additionally, *G. dentisursi* and *G. papilionis* showed high genetic similarity, suggesting potential synonymy (see Figure 2-4).

Figure 2-4 Phylogenetic Tree Proposed by Brady et al. (2014) for the Genus *Gibbsiella* Based on MLSA Using *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* Sequence Comparisons

2-3 Studies on Bacterial Canker in Iran

Following the first report of bacterial canker caused by *Erwinia nigrifluens* in walnut trees in Sari and Zagh Marz in 1989 (1368 in the Persian calendar), this bacterium has been documented across various Iranian regions, including Mazandaran, Golestan, Guilan, Alborz, Fars, Kurdistan, Kerman, Lorestan, and Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad (Rahimian, 1987; Baradaran and Ghasemi, 2004; Jamalzadeh et al., 2006; Harighi and Rahimian, 2006; Roshangar and Harighi, 2009; Asari et al., 2010; Amirsardari et al., 2015). Jamalzadeh et al. (2006) reported diversity among *B. nigrifluens* strains isolated from Mazandaran, Guilan, and Golestan provinces. Falahi Charkhabi et al. (2010) confirmed this diversity among strains from Kerman, Mazandaran, Golestan, Fars, and Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad provinces.

To date, various species of *Brenneria* and *Gibbsiella*, along with other *Yersiniaceae* family members, have been reported from oak, walnut, and ornamental trees exhibiting bleeding canker symptoms across Iran in recent years (Moradi-Amirabad et al., 2019; Bakhshi Ganje et al., 2020; Basavand et al., 2021). Bakhshi Ganje et al. (2020) documented isolates of *Brenneria goodwinii*, *B. roseae* subsp. *roseae*, *B. nigrifluens*, and *Gibbsiella* sp. associated with oak decline in Golestan and Mazandaran provinces. Sadeghi et al. (2019) isolated *B. nigrifluens* from various walnut-growing regions in Kerman province, also noting the presence of *Gibbsiella* species that may contribute to or exacerbate bacterial canker symptoms.

2-3-1 Occurrence of Bacterial Canker Caused by *G. quercinecans* in Iran

In 2021, a bacterial disease caused by *G. quercinecans*, exhibiting stem canker symptoms, was observed on walnut trees in East Azerbaijan, West Azerbaijan, and Zanjan provinces (Allahverdipour et al., 2021). While *G. quercinecans* is primarily associated with disease in oak trees, it can also induce canker in other tree species, similar to *B. nigrifluens*, which causes bacterial canker in walnut and can infect oak (Bakhshi Ganje et al., 2020). Recently, this bacterium has also been reported as a pathogen on Russian olive (*Elaeagnus angustifolia*), an ornamental plant (Basavand et al., 2021). Given the economic and ecological importance of walnut and oak trees, *G. quercinecans* is emerging as a critical threat to forest and nut trees in Iran alongside *B. nigrifluens*. This suggests potential overlap in factors driving the spread of these diseases, such as environmental conditions or common vectors. Investigating the potential causes of bacterial canker in oak and walnut trees could provide valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms of disease spread and inform effective control strategies for both hosts.

The present study aims to examine the predominant bacterial canker pathogens in walnut production regions of Iran that have received less attention, such as cities in Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Isfahan, and Fars provinces. Notably, limited research has been conducted on walnut and oak trees in these areas, particularly in Yasuj (walnut) in Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Khansar (walnut) in Isfahan, and Dasht-e Barm (oak) in Fars. The study seeks to elucidate the taxonomic positions of bacterial species using genotypic and phenotypic methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of their interrelationships.

Table 2-2 Earliest Reports of Bacterial Canker on Walnut Trees Caused by *Gibbsiella* Isolates

Region	Host	Pathogen	Identification Method	Source
Britain, Spain	<i>Quercus petraea</i> , <i>Q. robur</i>	<i>Gibbsiella quercinecans</i>	<i>gyrB</i> , DDH	Brady et al., 2010
California, USA	<i>Q. kelloggii</i>	<i>Gibbsiella greigii</i>	MLSA	Brady et al., 2014
Spain	<i>Q. robur</i> L.	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	<i>gyrB</i> , <i>atpD</i>	Gonzalez and Ciordia, 2020
Iran	<i>Q. castaneifolia</i> , <i>Q. macranthera</i>	<i>Gibbsiella</i> spp.	MLSA	Bakhshi Ganje et al., 2020
Iran	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	MLSA	Basavand et al., 2021
Lithuania	<i>Q. robur</i> L.	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	Real-time PCR	Zalkalns and Celma, 2021

Region	Host	Pathogen	Identification Method	Source
Poland	<i>Q. robur</i> L.	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	Real-time PCR	Tkaczyk et al., 2021
Switzerland	<i>Q. petraea</i>	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	16S rRNA, <i>gyrB</i>	Ruffner et al., 2020
Iran	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	<i>G. quercinecans</i>	MLSA	Allahverdi-pour et al., 2021

2-4 Importance of Taxonomic Studies: Challenges and Strategies

Taxonomic studies are crucial for the precise identification of pathogenic species and isolates. Identifying disease-causing bacteria requires diverse methods, including biochemical analysis, physiological assessments, nutritional tests, pathogenicity assays, and PCR-based techniques. This is particularly important as other bacterial species with similar colony morphologies are often isolated from walnut lesions, necessitating phenotypic and molecular evaluations for differentiation. Recent advancements in identification techniques have been significant. For instance, an alternative pathogenicity test using immature walnut fruit instead of walnut seedlings has been developed, overcoming the limitations of traditional stem inoculation assays, which typically require a month to yield results (Moretti and Buonauro, 2010). Additionally, Loreti et al. (2008) developed specific PCR primers for *B. nigrifluens* using M13 phage minisatellite sequences, significantly enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of rapid detection of this pathogen.

Traditional taxonomic classification of plant-pathogenic bacteria has relied on methods such as DNA-DNA hybridization and 16S rRNA sequencing. However, heterogeneous laboratory techniques and variable parameters have hindered the application of DNA-DNA hybridization, posing challenges in standardization, cost, and precise species identification (Almeida et al., 2010). Despite its high resolution in distinguishing closely related species, DNA-DNA hybridization has been surpassed by methods like whole genome sequencing and average nucleotide identity (ANI) comparisons, which offer greater efficiency. However, these approaches require significantly more resources and infrastructure than multi-locus sequence analysis (MLSA) and are more complex to implement for pathogen identification within microbial populations.

To address these challenges, MLSA has emerged as a valuable alternative, leveraging sequence data to provide higher resolution and reproducibility, with results serving as comparative benchmarks across studies. MLSA involves sequencing multiple gene loci, enabling differentiation of isolates at the subspecies level and overcoming traditional limitations.

Identifying plant-pathogenic bacteria remains a fundamental challenge in plant pathology due to species diversity, genetic variability, and adaptability. Conventional methods relying on phenotypic traits—such as morphology, biochemical tests, and growth patterns—are limited in distinguishing closely related species. In recent years, molecular biology techniques, particularly MLSA, have emerged as vital tools in prokaryotic classification, offering greater clarity and species identification within a genus. MLSA evolved from multi-locus sequence typing (MLST), initially developed for epidemiological studies of pathogenic bacteria. MLST focuses on the diversity of multiple housekeeping genes, assigning unique allele numbers to different sequences. MLSA integrates protein-coding gene analysis to achieve higher resolution at species and subspecies levels. Criteria for MLSA include selecting single-copy, universal, ubiquitous genes while avoiding those linked to pathogenicity. Concatenating aligned sequences of these genes enables robust phylogenetic analysis and precise isolate placement at the species level. Studies have highlighted MLSA's potential in prokaryotic classification as a viable

replacement for traditional DNA-DNA hybridization (Maiden et al., 1998). Comparing nucleotide sequences of multiple housekeeping genes across isolates offers greater diagnostic power than traditional methods due to varying evolutionary rates, enhancing phylogenetic tree inference and understanding evolutionary relationships among bacterial genera and species. Moreover, the development of computational tools and databases for analyzing large datasets and comparing results across studies has expedited the identification of new pathogens.

MLSA has been applied in several studies of plant-pathogenic bacteria to investigate their evolution and population genetics, including taxonomic studies of *Brenneria* and *Gibbsiella* (Brady et al., 2008; Brady et al., 2010). It is considered a practical, cost-effective, and accurate option among single-gene phylogenetic and whole-genome approaches, providing a suitable tool for assessing interspecies diversity. However, challenges remain in gene selection and primer design. Genes must encode stable, essential proteins and be less prone to rapid genetic changes, yet selecting a universal gene set that classifies all prokaryotes while distinguishing closely related species is difficult. Thus, gene sets are often tailored to specific taxa under study, ideally being single-copy, homologous, and ubiquitous within the genome (Zeigler, 2003; De Vos, 2011; Glaeser and Kämpfer, 2015). For example, Young et al. (2008) proposed *gyrB*, *rpoD*, *dnaK*, and *fyuA* for classifying *Xanthomonas*, refining its taxonomy to a level validated by subsequent studies. Brady et al. (2008) used *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* to update the taxonomy of *Enterobacteriaceae* genera, resolving long-standing classification issues for multiple species and facilitating global identification of new plant pathogens from this family by depositing amplified sequences in public databases.

2-5 Need for Comprehensive Studies on Bacterial Canker Pathogens of Walnut and Oak in Iran

Understanding the epidemiology, genetic diversity, and control measures for bacterial canker in walnut trees is essential for maintaining and enhancing walnut cultivation productivity in Iran. Previous studies using marker systems such as rep-PCR², IS50-PCR³, and RAPD⁴ have provided insights into the genetic diversity of *B. nigrifluens* in Iran, indicating potential geographic differentiation among strains (Falahi Charkhabi et al., 2010; Jamalzadeh et al., 2012). However, the lack of reproducible results, despite the disease's long-standing presence and significant damage to walnut orchards, has hindered the development of a unified national management strategy. Further research using advanced molecular techniques is necessary to comprehensively understand *B. nigrifluens* genetic diversity, establish a comparable genetic database nationwide, and develop effective disease management strategies to reduce economic losses and ensure sustainable walnut production in Iran, a historically significant global producer.

While MLSA excels in precise bacterial identification, it has limitations, as gene selection can influence result accuracy, and it may not suit all bacterial species due to genomic content and diversity differences (Maiden et al., 2013). To overcome these, researchers have developed alternative methods for bacterial identification, particularly at the subspecies level, using molecular markers like whole-genome sequencing (WGS⁵), single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP⁶) analysis, and multilocus variable-number tandem repeat analysis (MLVA⁷) (Lindstedt, 2005; Maquart et al., 2009; Leekitcharoenphon et al., 2014; Aanensen et al., 2016). These methods have shown promise in improving identification precision, especially where traditional MLSA lacks sufficient resolution among pathovars. Nevertheless, MLSA remains pivotal for identifying and classifying bacteria, particularly for emerging plant diseases

² Repetitive Sequence-Based PCR

³ Insertion Sequences-Based PCR

⁴ Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA

⁵ Whole Genome Sequencing

⁶ Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

⁷ MultiLocus Variable Number Tandem Repeat Analysis

requiring rapid, accurate pathogen detection. Its diagnostic strength stems from analyzing multiple conserved genomic genes, providing robust phylogenetic inference. In contrast, whole-genome sequencing, while offering high-resolution data, demands significant computational resources and costs (Schwarze et al., 2018). In developing countries like Iran, where plant disease research funding is limited, MLSA's cost-effectiveness, reproducibility, and reliability make it preferable for routine bacterial isolate identification. MLVA, targeting variable genomic regions, is prone to errors like convergence, potentially leading to misidentification, whereas MLSA's use of conserved housekeeping genes reduces such risks, offering a more reliable molecular typing method.

However, relying on a single conserved genomic region for species-level isolate differentiation is insufficient across all isolates, with different regions yielding varying results and inferences. Further studies on molecular epidemiology, taxonomy, and integrated management strategies for walnut and oak bacterial canker in Iran are essential to address these significant threats to strategic crop production. Epidemiological studies should focus on geographic distribution patterns and environmental factors influencing disease prevalence. Identifying potential vectors and transmission mechanisms between trees could also be insightful. Taxonomic studies using modern molecular methods can enhance species and isolate classification and differentiation. Finally, developing integrated disease management programs—including preventive, control, and therapeutic measures based on these findings—could effectively mitigate these threats.

Given the economic and ecological importance of walnut and oak, comprehensive and extensive studies in Iran are imperative. Such research could deepen understanding of these diseases' epidemiology and pathogenicity. Identifying and isolating native pathogen isolates in Iran, and studying their genetic and phenotypic traits, could provide valuable data for comparing genotypes and improving disease management. Establishing databases and genetic resource banks of native pathogens is also critical for future research facilitation, as accessing genetic data or isolates from other Iranian regions proved challenging during this study.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

3.1 Examination of Isolates in the Bacterial Collection at Vali-e-Asr University, Rafsanjan

To investigate the isolates associated with bacterial canker of walnut in various regions of Iran, isolates from the bacterial collection at Vali-e-Asr University, Rafsanjan, were utilized (Table 3-1). These isolates were retrieved from a -80°C storage and streaked onto Nutrient Agar Sucrose (NAS) medium containing 3% sucrose. Following incubation at 25°C for 24 to 48 hours, single-colony isolates were purified and subsequently used for further analyses.

Table 3-1 Accession Codes of Bacterial Canker-Associated Isolates in the Bacterial Collection at Vali-e-Asr University, Rafsanjan

Region	Isolate	Collection Code	Region	Isolate	Collection Code
Alborz	A1	VRU-1068	Golestan	G5	VRU-1810
Alborz	A2	VRU-2069	Hamedan	H1	VRU-1911
Alborz	A3	VRU-3070	Hamedan	H2	VRU-2012
Isfahan	E1	VRU-4071	Hamedan	H3	VRU-2113
Isfahan	E2	VRU-5072	Hamedan	H4	VRU-2214
Isfahan	E3	VRU-6073	Hamedan	H5	VRU-2315
Isfahan	E4	VRU-7074	Kerman	K1	VRU-2416
Isfahan	E5	VRU-8075	Kerman	K2	VRU-2517
Fars	F1	VRU-9076	Kerman	K3	VRU-2618
Fars	F2	VRU-1002	Kerman	K4	VRU-2719
Fars	F3	VRU-1103	Kerman	K5	VRU-2820
Fars	F4	VRU-1204	Kerman	K6	VRU-2921
Fars	F5	VRU-1305	Kerman	K7	VRU-3022
Golestan	G1	VRU-1406	Kerman	K8	VRU-3123
Golestan	G2	VRU-1507	Kerman	K9	VRU-3224
Golestan	G3	VRU-1608	Kerman	K10	VRU-3325
Golestan	G4	VRU-1709	Kurdistan	KO1	VRU-3426

Region	Isolate	Collection Code	Region	Isolate	Collection Code
Kurdistan	KO2	VRU-3527	Mazandaran	M4	VRU-3931
Mazandaran	M1	VRU-3628	Mazandaran	M5	VRU-4032
Mazandaran	M2	VRU-3729	Semnan	S1	VRU-4133
Mazandaran	M3	VRU-3830	Semnan	S2	VRU-4234

3-2 Biochemical Characterization of Isolates

For the identification of isolates in the bacterial collection at Vali-e-Asr University, Rafsanjan, various biochemical tests were performed following standard bacteriological methodologies (Schaad et al., 2001). A description of some of these tests is provided below.

3-2-1 Differential Culture Media

The colony color, morphology, and pigment production of each isolate were examined on Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar, Yeast Dextrose Calcium Carbonate (YDC) agar, and King's B medium (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-2 Gram Staining

The Gram reaction of the isolates was assessed using a 3% potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution following the method of Suslow et al. (1982).

3-2-3 Hypersensitivity Reaction in *Pelargonium*

A fresh bacterial suspension was prepared in sterile distilled water, and the turbidity was adjusted to 10^9 cfu/ml using a T80 UV/VIS Spectrophotometer (Spectrometer PG Instruments Ltd., UK) at 600 nm. A 1 mL suspension was injected into the abaxial surface of *Pelargonium* leaves using an insulin syringe. The development of a water-soaked lesion within 24 to 72 hours was considered a positive hypersensitivity response. Sterile distilled water was used as a negative control (Klement et al., 1964).

3-2-4 Oxidase Test

A 1% tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride solution was prepared in sterile distilled water, and sterile filter paper was saturated with the reagent. Fresh bacterial colonies were streaked onto the filter paper using a wooden applicator. The appearance of a purple color within 10 seconds was recorded as a positive reaction, whereas the absence of color change indicated a negative result (Kovacs, 1956).

3-2-5 Catalase Test

A drop of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) was placed on a microscope slide, and a bacterial colony was mixed into the droplet using a sterile wooden applicator. The formation of oxygen bubbles was considered a positive result (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-6 Aerobic/Anaerobic Growth

Aerobic and anaerobic growth was evaluated following the method of Hugh and Leifson (1953). Growth patterns were determined based on the color change of the medium from green to yellow or blue within one week. A yellow or blue color change in the tube without sterile mineral oil, along with no color change in the oil-sealed tube, indicated obligate aerobic growth. A color change in both tubes indicated facultative anaerobic growth.

3-2-7 Levan Production Test

Nutrient Agar Sucrose medium containing 5% sucrose was prepared and poured into sterile Petri dishes. After solidification, bacterial isolates were spot-inoculated. The presence of dome-shaped, mucoid colonies indicated a positive result (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-8 Gelatin Hydrolysis Test

Nutrient Agar medium containing 4% gelatin was prepared, and bacterial isolates were spot-inoculated. After one week, bacterial growth was removed using sterile cotton, and gelatin reagent (Appendix 1) was added to the surface. The formation of a clear halo around the colony was considered a positive result (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-9 Starch Hydrolysis Test

Nutrient Agar medium containing 2% starch was prepared and poured into sterile Petri dishes. Bacterial isolates were spot-inoculated, and after one week, bacterial growth was removed with sterile cotton. Lugol's iodine (Appendix 2) was added to the medium. The presence of a clear halo around the colony was recorded as a positive result (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-10 Esculin Hydrolysis Test

The appropriate culture medium (Appendix 3) was prepared, and bacterial isolates were spot-inoculated. Petri dishes were incubated at 25°C for 24 hours. A black coloration around the colonies was indicative of a positive reaction (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-11 Assessment of H₂S Production from Peptone, Cysteine, and Thiosulfate

Liquid YS medium (Appendix 4) was prepared, and after the separate addition of peptone, cysteine, and thiosulfate, the medium was autoclaved in test tubes. Following inoculation with the isolates, a sterile paper strip impregnated with 10% lead acetate was placed 1 cm above the surface of the medium. The blackening of the paper strip's tip indicated H₂S production, confirming a positive test result (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-12 Urease Test

The urease test medium (Appendix 5) was prepared in test tubes and autoclaved. Urea was added to the medium using a sterile syringe filter. After inoculating the isolates, the test tubes were incubated at room temperature. A color change in the medium to red indicated a positive reaction (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-2-13 Arginine Dihydrolase Test

The arginine dihydrolase test was conducted using Thornley medium (Appendix 6) in test tubes. After inoculation, the surface of the medium was covered with sterile liquid paraffin. The appearance of a red color after one week signified a positive test result (Thornley, 1960).

3-2-14 Utilization of Various Carbon Sources

Tests for the utilization of different carbon sources and acid production from various sugars were conducted using Ayer solid medium (Appendix 7) following standard protocols (Schaad et al., 2001).

3-3 Genotypic Analysis of the Isolates

For the molecular identification of isolates from the bacterial collection at Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan, a suspension of 500 µL was prepared from 24-hour cultures grown on nutrient agar (NA) in 1 mL microtubes. A 10% KOH solution (0.1 volume) was added to the suspension, which was then incubated in a laboratory water bath until clarified. The clarified suspensions were centrifuged at 10,000 × g for 3 to 5 minutes. The supernatant was transferred to a new microtube as the DNA sample (Arabi et al., 2006). These DNA samples were amplified and sequenced using 16S rRNA and *recA* primers. A

maximum-likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree was constructed, comparing the obtained sequences with those of closely related genera and species within the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. The primers used and the amplification conditions are provided in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2 Sequences of 16S rRNA and recA Primers and Their Annealing Temperatures

Primer	Sequence	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Reference
16S rRNA	F: AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG R: TTCTGCAGTCTAGAAGGAGGTGWTCAGCC	55	Hauben et al., 1998
recA	F: GARKCBTCNGGTAACVAC R: TTCGCYTTRCCCTGRCCRATC	47	Parkinson et al., 2009

3-4 Sampling

Based on the results of the identification of isolates obtained from the bacterial collection at Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan, sampling sites were selected. In the spring and summer of 2019, samples were collected from *Juglans regia* (walnut) orchards in the provinces of Hamedan, Lorestan, Isfahan, Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, and Fars. Trees exhibiting characteristic symptoms, including vertical trunk cracks, dark irregular lesions beneath the bark, and black exudates from wounds, were selected for sampling. Additionally, symptomatic *Quercus brantii* (Persian oak) trees in the Zagros Forest region and Dasht-e Barm, Kazerun County, Fars Province, displaying dark irregular wounds and foamy white exudates, were sampled (Figure 3-1). These symptoms were more frequently observed in mature trees in humid forested areas, while drier regions exhibited fewer symptoms. The geographic locations of the sampled cities and sites were recorded using GPS and are listed in Table 3-3.

Samples were collected using a gardening knife from the inner bark and soft living wood beneath the bark at various trunk locations, particularly near the canopy. The collected samples were placed in individual paper bags and transported to the laboratory for further analysis.

Figure 3-1 Characteristic symptoms of canker in walnut trees including irregular vertical cracks in the trunk and black exudate discharge (these symptoms in oak were accompanied by white foam-like masses as shown in the image).

Table 3-3 Geographical coordinates, sampling information, and resulting isolates

Sample Number	Region	Geographical Coordinates	Sampling Date	Sampling Site	Host	Isolate Number
TI-2019002	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229520, 50.302081	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF72
TI-2019004	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229469, 50.302054	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF74
TI-2019006	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229554, 50.301897	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF76
TI-2019007	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229579, 50.302067	21/05/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF77
TI-2019008	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229469, 50.302086	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF78
TI-2019009	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229387, 50.302047	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF79
TI-2019010	Isfahan, Khansar	33.229394, 50.302080	21/05/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF80
TI-2019011	Isfahan, Khansar	33.220045, 50.311946	21/05/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF81
TI-2019012	Isfahan, Khansar	33.219898, 50.311641	21/05/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF82
TF-2019019	Fars, Shiraz, Dokuhak	29.796416, 52.390369	07/07/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF63
TF-2019025	Fars, Sepidan, Bereshaneh	30.205303, 52.041307	08/07/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF59
TF-2019026	Fars, Sepidan, Bereshaneh	30.205216, 52.041201	08/07/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF62
TF-2019028	Fars, Sepidan, Bereshaneh	30.205313, 52.041731	08/07/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF68
TF-2019035	Fars, Kazerun, Dasht-e Barm	29.549237, 51.879478	09/07/2019	Inner bark	Oak	SF67

Sample Number	Region	Geographical Coordinates	Sampling Date	Sampling Site	Host	Isolate Number
TF-2019046	Fars, Kazerun, Dasht-e Barm	29.549985, 51.880028	09/07/2019	Inner bark	Oak	SF10
TK-2019063	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.61218, 51.33720	14/07/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF18
TK-2019064	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.611713, 51.337474	14/07/2019	Soft living tissue under bark	Walnut	SF29
TK-2019065	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.611397, 51.337623	14/07/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF30
TK-2019066	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.611301, 51.337670	14/07/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF31
TK-2019067	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.611995, 51.337230	14/07/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF34
TK-2019068	Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Yasuj, Buneh Sadat	30.611897, 51.337195	14/07/2019	Inner bark	Walnut	SF41

3-5 Isolation and Purification of Bacterial Isolates

Infected samples were washed under running water for one to two minutes and then surface-sterilized with 1% sodium hypochlorite (from commercial solution) for 30 seconds. The samples were rinsed with sterile distilled water, and after removing excess water, placed in Petri dishes and cut into smaller pieces using a sterile scalpel. A few drops of sterile distilled water were added, and the samples were placed on a laboratory shaker for 30 minutes at room temperature. A full loop of the suspension from the soaked samples was streaked onto Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) medium and incubated for 24 hours at 25°C. Small, metallic green single colonies were selected from each plate and cultured on Nutrient Agar containing 3% sucrose (NAS) medium (Bakhshi ganje et al., 2020).

3-6 Preservation of Isolates

For short-term preservation, a dense suspension of 24-hour bacterial cultures from NAS medium was prepared in sterile distilled water and stored at 4°C. For long-term preservation, a dense suspension of freshly cultured bacteria in liquid Nutrient Broth (NB) was mixed with sterile glycerol at a 1:1 ratio and stored at -80°C.

3-7 Hypersensitivity Reaction Test on Geranium Plants

A bacterial suspension with a concentration of 10^9 CFU/ml was prepared in sterile distilled water, which was determined using a spectrophotometer with an optical density of 0.8 at 600 nm wavelength. The suspension was injected using a 1 ml insulin syringe into the abaxial surface of geranium leaves between the main veins. The injection continued until it saturated a circular area of approximately 1 cm in

diameter. The appearance of water-soaked lesions 24-72 hours after inoculation was considered a positive reaction and indicated a hypersensitivity response.

3-8 Pathogenicity Test on Immature Walnut Fruit

Immature walnut fruits were surface-sterilized with 70% ethanol for 5 minutes and dried on sterile filter paper. A bacterial suspension with a concentration of 10^7 CFU/ml was injected using a sterile syringe with a needle into the mesocarp of immature walnut fruits with three replications, and sterile distilled water was used as a control. This concentration was determined using a spectrophotometer with an optical density of 0.1 at 600 nm wavelength. The standard isolate *Brenneria nigrifluens* (ICMP 20120) was used as a positive control. The inoculated walnuts were placed in plastic bags in a growth chamber at 28°C and 80% humidity. Daily observations were conducted to record necrosis symptoms for 12 days (Moretti and Buonauro, 2010).

3-9 Pathogenicity Test on Walnut Saplings

After 24 hours of bacterial growth on Nutrient Agar (NA) medium, a bacterial suspension with a concentration of 10^7 CFU/ml was prepared in sterile distilled water. Five-year-old walnut saplings, Chandler cultivar, were purchased from Novin Kesht Mazandaran nursery. The bacterial suspension was injected into young branches of the walnut saplings using a sterile syringe. Plastic bags were placed over the inoculated areas for one week. Each isolate was injected into two saplings. Sterile distilled water was used for control pots. The inoculated saplings were monitored daily in greenhouse conditions at 28°C with 80% humidity for one month.

3-10 Analysis of Phenotypic Characteristics of Isolates

The following tests were performed: Gram reaction using solubility in 3% potassium hydroxide (Suslow et al., 1982); aerobic and anaerobic growth test (Hugh and Leifson, 1953); oxidase test (Kovacs, 1965); morphology and fluorescent pigment production on King's B medium; metallic green halo production on EMB medium and pink pigment production on YDC medium; catalase test; levan production; urease activity; esculin, gelatin, and starch hydrolysis; H₂S gas production from cysteine, peptone, and thiosulfate; nitrate reduction (Schaad et al., 2001); indole production (Fahy and Hayward, 1983); production of reducing substances from sucrose (Schaad et al., 2001); and gas production from glucose (Rahimian, unpublished). Tests for utilization of various carbon sources and acid production from different sugars were conducted on solid Ayer's medium according to standard methods (Schaad et al., 2001). The standard strain *B. nigrifluens* (ICMP 20120) was used as a positive control alongside other isolates.

3-11 Numerical Analysis

The similarity matrix was constructed based on the results of the hypersensitivity test on geranium plants, pathogenicity test on immature walnut fruits, and biochemical characteristics of the isolates. In this matrix, positive results were assigned a value of one and negative results a value of zero. Data analysis was performed using PAST software (Hammer et al., 2001). Cluster analysis was conducted by determining Jaccard's similarity coefficient, and a dendrogram was constructed using the Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA) algorithm (Sneath and Sokal, 1973).

3-12 Genotypic Analysis of Isolates

3-12-1 Genomic DNA Extraction

DNA isolation was performed using the CTAB method of William et al. (2012). Isolates were cultured on nutrient agar medium and incubated for 24 hours at 28°C. A dense suspension of bacterial cells (10^{12} CFU/ml) was prepared in 600 µl of CTAB buffer (Appendix 8). The suspension was boiled in a laboratory water bath at 65-70°C for 30 minutes, and an equal volume of chilled chloroform-isoamyl alcohol (1:1) was added to the CTAB buffer. The samples were centrifuged at 13,000×g for 15 minutes,

after which the supernatant was removed and transferred to a new microtube. An equal volume of chilled isopropanol was added to the supernatant and stored at -20°C for one hour. Centrifugation was performed at 13,000×g for 15 minutes, then all microtube contents were emptied and 1000 µl of 70% ethanol was added. The nucleic acid pellet was obtained after 10 minutes of centrifugation at 13,000×g, and after emptying the contents and complete evaporation, 100 µl of sterile distilled water was added to each microtube and stored at -4°C for 24 hours. Genomic DNA samples were stored at -20°C until use in polymerase chain reaction.

3-12-2 Evaluation of Extracted DNA Quality

The composition of extracted DNA was determined spectrophotometrically using a NanoDrop 1000 with light absorption at 260 nm wavelength. The purity of DNA from protein and polysaccharide contamination was assessed by estimating the absorption ratios at A260/A280 and A260/A230, respectively. Additionally, the quality of extracted DNA was evaluated by electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel using RedSafe for staining (Aboul-Maaty and Oraby, 2019).

3-12-3 Molecular Identification of Isolates Using *B. nigrifluens* Specific Primers

For the identification of *B. nigrifluens* species, the primer pair (C3, F1) capable of amplifying 255 base pairs was used (Table 3-4). The polymerase chain reaction was performed in a final volume of 25 µl containing 10.5 µl of deionized distilled water, 12.5 µl of Ampliqon Taq DNA Polymerase 2x ready reaction mixture, 0.12 µM of forward specific primer, 0.12 µM of reverse specific primer, and 1 µl of extracted DNA (Table 3-5).

Table 3-4 *Brenneria nigrifluens* species-specific primers

Primer	Primer Sequence (5'-3')	Reference
F1	CCT GCG CCA TGT TGC CAG ATC GCT AT	Loreti et al., 2008
C3	ACC TGA GTA GCA GTT TCG ACT ATT T	

Table 3-5 PCR conditions with specific primers C3, F1

Number of Cycles	Stage	Temperature (°C)	Duration (seconds)
1	Initial Denaturation	95	300
	Denaturation	94	30
35	Annealing	60	45
	Extension	72	45
1	Final Extension	72	600

3-12-4 Electrophoresis of PCR Amplified Products

The PCR products were electrophoresed on 1% agarose gel with TBE buffer (Appendix 9) using an ATTA-WSE-3200 electrophoresis device at 80 volts for 45 minutes, and a 100 kb weight marker (Thermo Scientific SM0241) was used. The resulting electrophoresis patterns were observed, photographed, and recorded using a UV transilluminator equipped with a camera.

3-12-5 Selection of Housekeeping Genes for Amplification and Sequencing

For more precise examination of the taxonomic position of representative isolates, housekeeping genes including *infB*, *rpoB*, *gyrB*, and *atpD* were selected, and corresponding fragments from these isolates were amplified using polymerase chain reaction. Primer sequences and PCR conditions are presented in Tables 3-6 and 3-7.

Table 3-6 Primer sequences of housekeeping genes for PCR reaction

Primer	Primer Sequence (5'-3')	Reference
gyrB 01-F	TAA RTT YGA YGA YAA CTC YTA YAA AGT	Brady et al., 2008
gyrB 02-R	CMC CYT CCA CCA RGT AMA GTT	
rpoB CM7-F	AAC CAG TTC CGC GTT GGC CTG	Brady et al., 2008
rpoB CM31b-R	CCT GAA CAA CAC GCT CGG A	
infB 01-F	ATY ATG GGH HAY GTH GAY CA	Brady et al., 2008
infB 02-R	ACK GAG TAR TAA GGC AGA TCC A	
atpD 01-F	RTA ATY GGM GCS GTR GTN GAY GT	Brady et al., 2008
atpD 02-R	TCA TCC GCM GGW ACR TAW AYN GCC TG	

Table 3-7 PCR procedure for amplification of housekeeping genes

Number of Cycles	Stage	Temperature (°C)	Duration (seconds)
1	Initial Denaturation	95	300
	Denaturation	94	30
30	Annealing	55	45
	Extension	72	45
1	Final Extension	72	600

3-12-6 Sequencing and Multilocus Sequence Analysis (MLSA)

Amplified fragments from selected isolates in the polymerase chain reaction were sent to Microsynth (Switzerland) for purification and sequencing. The sequenced fragments were manually corrected in comparison with available reference genomes using Geneious Prime 2019 v1.8.0 software, and low-quality nucleotides were removed. Multiple sequence alignments were performed using the ClustalW tool in Geneious Prime 2019 v1.8.0 software with sequences of similar regions, and both ends of the sequences were trimmed. The corrected sequences were submitted to the NCBI database, and their accession numbers were obtained. For dendrogram construction, Maximum Likelihood (ML) method using Phylosuite v1.2.2 software and IQ-TREE 2.2.0 tool, and Maximum Parsimony (MP) method using PAUP 4.0a software were employed for each gene separately and in a concatenated manner (Zhang et al., 2020; Minh et al., 2020). Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony methods were performed with 1000 bootstrap replicates. Branches with bootstrap values below 50% were collapsed. Bayesian analysis was conducted using MrBayes 3.2.6 software (Ronquist et al., 2012) with the MCMC

method for 10^7 generations with a sampling frequency of 100, and for tree construction and posterior probability calculation, 25% of initial samples were discarded.

The appropriate substitution model for dendrogram construction for Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian analysis methods was selected using the ModelFinder tool (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017) available in Phylosuite v1.2.2 software based on AIC.

3-12-7 Amino Acid Sequence Analysis

To analyze the amino acid sequences resulting from the amplification of nucleotide sequences of housekeeping genes, the nucleotide sequences were translated using Geneious Prime 2019 v1.8.0 software and then aligned with the ClustalW tool in the same software. The resulting amino acid translations were concatenated using Phylosuite v1.2.2 software (a total of 812 amino acids). The concatenated amino acid dendrogram was constructed using the JTTDCMut substitution model with equal base frequencies and free rate variation (R) among sites (6 categories). The amino acid substitution model was also selected using the ModelFinder tool based on AIC.

3-12-8 Cladogram Construction

For cladogram construction, TreeGraph 2.15.0-887 beta software (Stöver et al., 2010) and the iTOL web tool were used (Letunic and Bork, 2021). This method was performed using the Maximum Likelihood tree as the base tree and adding bootstrap values and posterior probabilities obtained from Maximum Parsimony and Bayesian methods to it.

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

4-1 Examination of Isolates Obtained from the Bacterial Collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan

In this study, isolates associated with walnut canker disease were initially obtained from the bacterial collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan. These isolates were collected from key walnut cultivation regions across Iran, including the provinces of Alborz, Mazandaran, Golestan, Semnan, Kurdistan, Isfahan, Fars, and Kerman.

The prepared isolates were examined using biochemical methods, with the results detailed in Table 4-1. All isolates demonstrated the ability to induce symptoms on immature walnut fruits and were confirmed as pathogenic. For molecular identification, segments of the 16S rRNA and *recA* genomic regions were amplified and registered in the NCBI database (Table 4-2). These sequences were compared with similar regions from closely related genera and species within the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. The results indicated a 100% match with standard isolates of *Brenneria nigrifluens* (Figures 4-1 and 4-2).

Given that only four prior studies in Iran had provided 16S rRNA sequences, these sequences were retrieved from the gene bank and compared with those of the isolates obtained from the collection. Phylogenetic trees were constructed based on the maximum likelihood method, revealing that the isolates from the collection exhibited differences in some cases from those reported in previous Iranian studies (Figure 4-3). In this comparison, isolates from Fars province were more closely related to those reported by Allahverdipour et al. (2021), while isolates from Kerman province showed greater similarity to those documented by Sadeghi et al. (2019). Isolates from the provinces of Alborz, Isfahan, Kurdistan, Hamadan, Golestan, Mazandaran, and Semnan clustered together, distinct from other Iranian isolates and the standard *B. nigrifluens* DSM 30175 strain.

The findings confirmed that isolates obtained from various regions of Iran, exhibiting visible symptoms of walnut bark canker, belonged to *B. nigrifluens*. The genetic diversity of these isolates had previously been assessed by Falahi Charkhabi et al. (2010) and Jamalzade et al. (2012). Genotypic identification using specific primers further confirmed that all isolates belonged to the species *B. nigrifluens*. Since studies in Iran, even in recent years, have predominantly focused on the aforementioned regions where *B. nigrifluens* has been the dominant pathogen, less-studied areas were selected as new sampling sites for this research.

Figure 4-2 Phylogenetic tree constructed from the comparison of *recA* region sequences of isolates from the bacterial collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan with sequences of this region from other closely related species and genera within the *Enterobacteriaceae* family.

Figure 4-3 Phylogenetic tree constructed from the comparison of 16S rRNA region sequences of isolates from the bacterial collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan with sequences of this region from similar species in previous studies conducted and available in Iran (green represents isolates prepared from the collection; red, pink, gold, and blue represent isolates from other Iranian studies).

Table 4-1 Biochemical Results of Isolates Obtained from the Bacterial Collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan Compared to the Standard Strain

Test	Isolates from the Bacterial Collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
Gram reaction	-	-
Oxidase	+	+
Aerobic/Anaerobic growth	Facultative anaerobe	Facultative anaerobe
Pink pigment production on YDC	-	-

Test	Isolates from the Bacterial Collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
Metallic green sheen on EMB	+	+
Levan production	-	-
Hypersensitivity on geranium	+	+
Urease	-	-
H ₂ S production from peptone	-	-
H ₂ S production from cysteine	+	+
H ₂ S production from thiosulfate	+	+
Esculin hydrolysis	+	+
Gelatin hydrolysis	-	-
Starch hydrolysis	-	-
Acid production from:		
Arbutin	+	+
Dulcitol	-	-
Salicin	+	+
Melibiose	+	+
D-Xylose	+	+
D-Adonitol	-	-
D-Arabitol	-	-
D-Ribose	+	+
D-Mannose	+	+
D-Galactose	+	+
D-Mannitol	+	+
D-Fructose	+	+

Test	Isolates from the Bacterial Collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
D-Raffinose	+	+
D-Sorbitol	+	+
D-Arabinose	+	+
L-Sorbose	-	-
L-Rhamnose	+	+

Table 4-2 Accession Numbers of 16S rRNA and *recA* Region Sequences in the Gene Bank

Isolate	16S rRNA Accession Number	<i>recA</i> Accession Number	Collection Code	Isolate Code in Phylograms
A1	OR527300	OR532586	VRU-1068	ALBORZ_A1
A2	OR527301	-	VRU-2069	ALBORZ_A2
A3	OR527302	-	VRU-3070	ALBORZ_A3
E1	OR527303	OR532585	VRU-4071	ISFAHAN_E1
E2	OR527304	-	VRU-5072	ISFAHAN_E2
E3	OR527305	-	VRU-6073	ISFAHAN_E3
E4	OR527306	-	VRU-7074	ISFAHAN_E4
E5	OR527307	-	VRU-8075	ISFAHAN_E5
F1	OR527308	OR532584	VRU-9076	FARS_F1
F2	OR527309	-	VRU-1002	FARS_F2
F3	OR527310	-	VRU-1103	FARS_F3
F4	OR527311	-	VRU-1204	FARS_F4
F5	OR527312	-	VRU-1305	FARS_F5
G1	OR527313	OR532583	VRU-1406	GOLESTAN_G1
G2	OR527314	-	VRU-1507	GOLESTAN_G2
G3	OR527315	-	VRU-1608	GOLESTAN_G3
G4	OR527316	-	VRU-1709	GOLESTAN_G4
G5	OR527317	-	VRU-1810	GOLESTAN_G5

Isolate	16S rRNA Accession Number	<i>recA</i> Accession Number	Collection Code	Isolate Code in Phylograms
H1	OR527318	OR532582	VRU-1911	HAMADAN_H1
H2	OR527319	-	VRU-2012	HAMADAN_H2
H3	OR527320	-	VRU-2113	HAMADAN_H3
H4	OR527321	-	VRU-2214	HAMADAN_H4
H5	OR527322	-	VRU-2315	HAMADAN_H5
K1	OR527323	OR532581	VRU-2416	Kerman_K1
K2	OR527324	-	VRU-2517	Kerman_K2
K3	OR527325	-	VRU-2618	Kerman_K3
K4	OR527326	-	VRU-2719	Kerman_K4
K5	OR527327	-	VRU-2820	Kerman_K5
K6	OR527328	-	VRU-2921	Kerman_K6
K7	OR527329	-	VRU-3022	Kerman_K7
K8	OR527330	-	VRU-3123	Kerman_K8
K9	OR527331	-	VRU-3224	Kerman_K9
K10	OR527332	-	VRU-3325	Kerman_K10
KO1	OR527333	OR532580	VRU-3426	Kurdestan_KO1
KO2	OR527334	-	VRU-3527	Kurdestan_KO2
M1	OR527335	OR532579	VRU-3628	MAZANDARAN_M1
M2	OR527336	-	VRU-3729	MAZANDARAN_M2
M3	OR527337	-	VRU-3830	MAZANDARAN_M3
M4	OR527338	-	VRU-3931	MAZANDARAN_M4
M5	OR527339	-	VRU-4032	MAZANDARAN_M5
S1	OR527340	OR532578	VRU-4133	SEMNAN_S1
S2	OR527341	-	VRU-4234	SEMNAN_S2

2-4 Sampling, Isolation, and Purification of Isolates

Based on biochemical and molecular results obtained from bacterial isolates received from the bacterial collection of Vali-e-Asr University of Rafsanjan, it was determined that these isolates belonged to the bacterium *B. nigrifluens*. Since these isolates were collected from regions where sufficient studies on their distribution and genetic diversity had been conducted, sampling was carried out in 1398 (2019) from major walnut-growing areas in central Iranian provinces that had been less studied, including Hamadan (Tuiserkan), Lorestan (Aleshtar and Khorramabad), Isfahan (Khansar), Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad (Yasuj), and the oak forests of the Zagros region and Dasht-e Barmn (Kazerun) in Fars Province. Infected samples were collected from trunks and main branches showing canker symptoms accompanied by black exudate in walnut trees, and from symptomatic oak trees with foam-like white exudate.

Longitudinal cracks, irregular black spots beneath the bark surface, and flowing black exudate were characteristic symptoms of trees from which isolations were performed. The number of symptomatic trees in Hamadan and Lorestan provinces was limited, especially in Hamadan Province where irrigation management and tree maintenance were conducted according to specific principles and programs. The difference in canker symptoms between oak trees and walnut trees was the secretion of white foam-like masses at wound sites, and identical symptoms were observed in all oak trees in the Dasht-e Barm region.

A total of 100 infected plant tissues were collected, from which 80 isolates were obtained. Single colonies were selected based on color, morphology, and production of metallic green halos on EMB medium, and then streaked on NAS medium for purification (Figures 4-4 and 4-5).

Figure 4-4 Streak culture from suspension of soaked samples on EMB medium

Figure 4-5 Streak culture for purification on NAS medium

3-4 Hypersensitivity Reaction Test on Geranium Plants

All obtained isolates were injected into the lower surface of geranium leaves, and after 24 to 72 hours post-injection, only 21 isolates showed water-soaking symptoms at the injection sites (Table 3-4).

4-4 Pathogenicity Test on Immature Walnut Fruits

The development of symptoms on immature walnut fruits was monitored daily for up to 12 days after inoculation. From the second day, water-soaked areas appeared at the injection sites, creating reddish-brown symptoms. By day 12, symptoms reached maximum severity with complete blackening of the fruit accompanied by bacterial ooze. In total, 21 isolates demonstrated pathogenicity over the 12-day period. Fruits inoculated with sterile distilled water (control) showed no disease symptoms. Isolates capable of inducing disease symptoms in immature walnut fruits were selected as representative isolates for further studies in subsequent stages (Figure 4-6). From all infected tissues, isolates with the initial form were grown on nutrient agar medium, and pathogenicity was confirmed according to Koch's postulates.

Figure 4-6 Symptoms of pathogenicity test on immature walnut fruit, in order from left to right: second, fourth, sixth, eighth, and twelfth days, and control treatment (no symptoms developed on the control)

4-5 Pathogenicity Test on Walnut Seedlings

From the twenty-one isolates capable of causing disease on immature fruits, suspensions were prepared and injected into 5-year-old walnut seedlings to assess pathogenicity in trees. After 10 to 15 days post-injection, water-soaked lesions appeared at inoculation sites. These symptoms progressively expanded,

and after 30 to 45 days, the injection sites blackened. Control seedlings injected with sterile distilled water instead of isolate suspension showed no symptoms (Figure 4-7). Koch's postulates were confirmed by re-isolating bacteria similar to those initially injected.

Figure 4-7 Pathogenicity symptoms on five-year-old walnut seedlings (no symptoms developed in the control plant (right) injected with sterile distilled water)

4-6 Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of Isolates

Isolates capable of inducing disease on immature fruits and walnut seedlings were Gram-negative, oxidase-negative, catalase-positive, and facultative anaerobes, able to grow on nutrient agar containing 5% sucrose. The colonies were convex, cream-white, circular with smooth margins, and could produce metallic green halos on EMB medium. These isolates were unable to produce pink pigment on YDC medium. The pathogenic isolates were divided into two groups based on differences in certain biochemical tests. The first group could produce H_2S from cysteine and thiosulfate and were capable of hydrolyzing esculin. They could also produce acid from arbutin, trehalose dihydrate, salicin, melibiose, D-xylose, D-ribose, D-mannose, D-galactose, D-mannitol, D-fructose, D-raffinose, D-sorbitol, D-arabinose, L-arabinose, and L-rhamnose. Group one isolates were negative for levan production, urease, indole production, nitrate reduction, H_2S production from peptone, gelatin and starch hydrolysis, reducing substances production from sucrose, and gas production from glucose. They were unable to produce acid from dulcitol, D-adonitol, D-arabitol, and L-sorbose, and showed variable results in acid production from myo-inositol. Based on these results, the first group showed highest similarity to the standard strain of *B. nigrifluens* (ICMP 20120), whereas the second group was negative for levan production, nitrate reduction, and H_2S production from cysteine and thiosulfate. They could produce acid from myo-inositol but were unable to produce acid from dulcitol and D-adonitol. Consequently, the second group was classified as "*Brenneria*-like" due to characteristics similar to *B. nigrifluens* but with the aforementioned differences from the first group. The results of biochemical tests for both groups alongside the standard strain are presented in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Biochemical characteristics of pathogenic isolates

Characteristic	" <i>Brenneria-like</i> " group (SF63, SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, SF76)	" <i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> " group (SF10, SF68, SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59, SF62)	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
Gram reaction	-	-	-
Oxidase	+	+	+
Aerobic/anaerobic growth	Facultative anaerobe	Facultative anaerobe	Facultative anaerobe
Pink pigment production on YDC medium	-	-	-
Fluorescent pigment production	-	-	-
Metallic green halo production on EMB medium	+	+	+
Levan production	+	-	-
Hypersensitivity reaction on geranium plant	+	+	+
Pathogenicity on immature walnut fruit	+	+	+
Pathogenicity on 5-year-old walnut seedling	+	+	+
Urease	-	-	-
Indole production	-	-	-
Nitrate reduction	+	-	-
H ₂ S production from peptone	-	-	-
H ₂ S production from cysteine	-	+	+
H ₂ S production from thiosulfate	-	+	+

Characteristic	" <i>Brenneria-like</i> " group (SF63, SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, SF76)	" <i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> " group (SF10, SF68, SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59, SF62)	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
Esculin hydrolysis	+	+	+
Gelatin hydrolysis	-	-	-
Starch hydrolysis	-	-	-
Production of reducing substances from sucrose	-	-	-
Gas production from glucose	-	-	-
Acid production from:			
Arbutin	+	+	+
Trehalose dihydrate	+	+	+
Dulcitol	-	-	-
Salicin	+	+	+
Melibiose	+	+	+
Myo-inositol	+	Variable	Variable
D-xylose	+	+	+
D-adonitol	-	-	-
D-arabitol	+	-	-
D-ribose	+	+	+
D-mannose	+	+	+
D-galactose	+	+	+
D-mannitol	+	+	+
D-fructose	+	+	+
D-raffinose	+	+	+
D-sorbitol	+	+	+
D-arabinose	+	+	+

Characteristic	" <i>Brenneria-like</i> " group (SF63, SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, SF76)	" <i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> " group (SF10, SF68, SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59, SF62)	<i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> (ICMP 20120)
L-arabinose	+	+	+
L-sorbose	+	-	-
L-rhamnose	+	+	+

4-7 Numerical Analysis

Eighty isolates collected during this study were analyzed based on results from hypersensitivity tests, pathogenicity tests on immature walnut fruits, and biochemical characteristics. A data matrix was created based on positive or negative results, assigning the value 1 for positive and 0 for negative results. Based on this data matrix, a dendrogram was constructed using the UPGMA method with Jaccard's similarity coefficient (Figure 4-8). According to the dendrogram, 21 isolates showing high similarity to the standard strain of *B. nigrifluens* were selected. The first group of isolates (SF10, SF68, SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59, SF62) was designated as the "*B. nigrifluens*" group, and the second group (SF63, SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, SF76) was designated as the "*Brenneria-like*" group (Figure 4-8).

Figure 4-8 UPGMA dendrogram constructed using Jaccard's similarity coefficient based on data matrix analysis of hypersensitivity tests, pathogenicity tests on immature walnut fruits, and biochemical characteristics of isolates

4-8 Polymerase Chain Reaction

4-8-1 DNA Extraction

Three microliters of DNA extracted from isolates produced distinct high molecular weight bands when electrophoresed on 1% agarose gel, indicating good quality of the extracted DNA (Figure 4-9).

Figure 4-9 Quality assessment of extracted DNA by electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel (1 kb Thermo Scientific molecular weight marker was used on the left)

4-8-2 Molecular Detection of *B. nigrifluens* Isolates

Isolates belonging to both "*B. nigrifluens*" and "*Brenneria*-like" groups, along with the standard strain, were amplified using the specific primer pair C3, F1. In the first group, a 255 base pair fragment was amplified, confirming these isolates' affiliation with the *B. nigrifluens* group. This fragment was not amplified in the second group, which also differed in some biochemical tests, despite three repetitions of the test. Consequently, they were classified as an independent group distinct from *B. nigrifluens* (Figure 4-10).

Figure 4-10 Use of specific primer pair C3, F1 to examine isolates from both "*Brenneria nigrifluens*" and "*Brenneria*-like" groups, along with the standard strain *Brenneria nigrifluens* (ICMP 20120) (Red rectangles indicate non-specific fragment amplification in isolates belonging to the "*Brenneria*-like" group in three replicates)

4-9 Multilocus Sequence Analysis

Among the representative isolates, SF72, SF74, SF76, SF77, SF78, SF79, SF80, SF81, and SF82 were isolated from Isfahan Province; SF59, SF67, and SF68 from Fars Province; and SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, and SF41 from Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad Province. The representative isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77 (Isfahan), SF59 (Fars) belonged to the "*B. nigrifluens*" group, and isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), SF67 (Fars), SF72, SF74, and SF76 (Isfahan) belonged to the "*Brenneria*-like" group.

For multilocus sequence typing of representative isolates, and based on the study by Brady et al. (2008), four genomic regions—*gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD*—were selected for amplification and comparison.

4-9-1 Amplification and Sequencing of *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* Genes

Sequencing of portions of the housekeeping genes *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* was performed according to primers suggested by Brady et al. (2008), and after editing, the sequences were submitted to the NCBI database. Tables 4-4 and 4-5 present the accession numbers of these sequences for the "*B. nigrifluens*" and "*Brenneria*-like" groups, respectively. Sequence comparison in GenBank using the BLAST tool showed similarity of isolates SF59, SF77, SF78, SF79, SF80, SF81, and SF82 with known species of *B. nigrifluens*, and isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, and SF76 with the known species *Gibbsiella quercinecans*.

Table 4-4 GenBank accession numbers for sequences of representative isolates from the "*Brenneria nigrifluens*" group

<i>atpD</i>	<i>infB</i>	<i>gyrB</i>	Host	Sequence name
OR077384	OR077377	OR077370	Walnut	SF59
OR077385	OR077378	OR077371	Walnut	SF77
OR077386	OR077379	OR077372	Walnut	SF78
OR077387	OR077380	OR077373	Walnut	SF79
OR077388	OR077381	OR077374	Walnut	SF80
OR077389	OR077382	OR077375	Walnut	SF81
OR077390	OR077383	OR077376	Walnut	SF82

Table 4-5 GenBank accession numbers for sequences of representative isolates from the "*Brenneria*-like" group

<i>atpD</i>	<i>infB</i>	<i>rpoB</i>	<i>gyrB</i>	Host	Sequence name
MZ502327	MZ502347	MZ502355	MZ502337	Walnut	SF18
MZ502328	MZ502348	MZ502356	MZ502338	Walnut	SF29
MZ502329	MZ502349	MZ502357	MZ502339	Walnut	SF30
OP821994	OP821991	MZ502358	MZ502340	Walnut	SF31
MZ502330	OP821992	MZ502359	MZ502341	Walnut	SF34
MZ502331	MZ502350	MZ502360	MZ502342	Walnut	SF41
MZ502332	OP821993	MZ502361	MZ502343	Oak	SF67
MZ502334	MZ502352	MZ502363	MZ502344	Walnut	SF72
MZ502335	MZ502353	MZ502364	MZ502345	Walnut	SF74

<i>atpD</i>	<i>infB</i>	<i>rpoB</i>	<i>gyrB</i>	Host	Sequence name
MZ502336	MZ502354	MZ502365	MZ502346	Walnut	SF76

4-9-2 Selection of Phylogenetic Methods and Models

The nucleotide substitution models selected for maximum likelihood analysis of each gene and each isolate group are presented separately in Table 4-6.

Table 4-6 Nucleotide substitution models in maximum likelihood analyses for each gene.

Gene	Group “ <i>Brenneria nigrifluens</i> ”	Group “ <i>Brenneria-like</i> ”
<i>gyrB</i>	TIM2+F+R5	GTR+G4+F
<i>rpoB</i>	-	SYM+I+G4
<i>infB</i>	TIM2e+R10	GTR+I+G4+F
<i>atpD</i>	GTR+F+R7	SYM+R6

For selecting appropriate substitution models for dendrogram construction using maximum likelihood and Bayesian analysis methods, ModelFinder tool (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017) available in Phylosuite v1.2.2 software was used based on the AIC criterion.

4-9-3 Amplification, Sequencing, and Phylogenetic Analysis of the *gyrB* Gene

The *gyrB* gene was selected from *B. nigrifluens* group isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59 and from *Brenneria-like* group isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, and SF76. Fragments of 538 and 545 base pairs were amplified and sequenced for each group, respectively. Using BLAST software, they were compared and aligned with other sequences available in GenBank. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using the Maximum Likelihood (ML) method with 1000 bootstrap replicates separately for the two isolate groups. Isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77 (Isfahan), SF59 (Fars) showed 100% similarity with various *B. nigrifluens* species, especially the standard strain *B. nigrifluens* LMG 2694 (Figure 4-11), and isolates SF67 (Fars), SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), SF72, SF74, and SF76 (Isfahan) showed 100% affiliation with various *G. quercinecans* strains (Figure 4-12). Isolates SF67 (Fars) and SF76 (Isfahan) were placed in the cluster belonging to the genus *Gibbsiella*; however, they did not show high similarity to any particular strain of this genus. Isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, and SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad) showed 70% similarity to strain *G. quercinecans* LMG 25502, and isolates SF72 and SF74 (Isfahan) showed 63% similarity to strain *G. quercinecans* BW 2/28.

Figure 4-12 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *gyrB* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates

4-9-4 Amplification, Sequencing, and Phylogenetic Analysis of the *rpoB* Gene

The *rpoB* gene was selected from *B. nigrifluens* group isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59 and from *Brenneria*-like group isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, and SF76. Fragments of 637 base pairs were amplified and sequenced only in the *Brenneria*-like group. Using BLAST software, they were compared and aligned with other sequences available in GenBank. Based on phylogenetic analysis of partial *rpoB* genomic region sequences in representative isolates using the Maximum Likelihood method, isolates SF67 (Fars), SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), SF72, SF74, and SF76 (Isfahan) showed 78% affiliation with various *G. quercinecans* strains (Figure 4-13). Only isolates SF67 (Fars) and SF76 (Isfahan) were placed in a separate cluster with 63% similarity alongside strain *G. quercinecans* N78. This genomic region could not be amplified in *B. nigrifluens* group isolates despite repeated attempts under various conditions, which was also observed previously in the study by Moradi Amirabad et al. (2020).

Figure 4-13 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *rpoB* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates

4-9-5 Amplification, Sequencing, and Phylogenetic Analysis of the *infB* Gene

The *infB* gene was selected from *B. nigrifluens* group isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59 and from *Brenneria*-like group isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, and SF76. Fragments of 615 base pairs were amplified and sequenced. Using BLAST software, they were compared and aligned with other sequences available in GenBank. Based on phylogenetic analysis of partial *infB* genomic region sequences in representative isolates using the Maximum Likelihood method, isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77 (Isfahan), SF59 (Fars) showed 100% similarity with various *B. nigrifluens* species, especially the standard strain *B. nigrifluens* LMG 2694 (Figure 4-14), and isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad) showed 98% similarity with each other and 65% similarity with the cluster comprising strains *G. quercinecans* LMG 25501, *G. quercinecans* N78, and *G. quercinecans* LMG 25502 (Figure 4-15). Isolates SF72 and SF74 (Isfahan) were placed alongside strain *G. quercinecans* BW 2/28 with 71% similarity. Isolates SF67

(Fars) and SF76 (Isfahan) were placed in the cluster belonging to the genus *Gibbsiella* with 59% similarity.

Figure 4-14 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *infB* for *Brenneria nigrifluens* group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates (scale indicates nucleotide substitutions per site)

Figure 4-15 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *infB* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates

4-9-6 Amplification, Sequencing, and Phylogenetic Analysis of the *atpD* Gene

The *atpD* gene was selected from *B. nigrifluens* group isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77, SF59 and from *Brenneria*-like group isolates SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41, SF67, SF72, SF74, and SF76. A fragment of 642 base pairs was amplified and sequenced. Using BLAST software, they were compared and aligned with other sequences available in GenBank. Based on phylogenetic analysis of partial *atpD* genomic region sequences in representative isolates using the Maximum Likelihood method, isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77 (Isfahan), SF59 (Fars) showed 100% similarity with various *B. nigrifluens* species, especially the standard strain *B. nigrifluens* LMG 2694 (Figure 4-16), and isolates SF67 (Fars), SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), SF72, SF74, and SF76 (Isfahan) showed similarity with various *G. quercinecans* strains (Figure 4-17). However, this genomic region did not provide adequate differentiation for the *Brenneria*-like group isolates. Only isolates SF67 (Fars) and SF76 (Isfahan) were placed in a separate cluster with 64%

similarity alongside strain *G. quercinecans* BW 2/28, and isolates SF72 and SF74 (Isfahan) were placed in the cluster comprising strains *G. quercinecans* LMG 25500 and *G. quercinecans* LMG 25502 with 63% similarity.

Tree scale: 1

Figure 4-16 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *atpD* for *Brenneria nigrifluens* group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates (scale indicates nucleotide substitutions per site)

Figure 4-17 Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of housekeeping gene *atpD* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates with 1000 bootstrap replicates

4-9-7 Construction and Phylogenetic Analysis of Concatenated Sequences

As explained in detail, using only one genomic region for differentiating isolates at the species level is insufficient for all isolates, and the selection of different regions provides different results and inferences. Therefore, for more precise analysis using Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST), the sequences of each region were concatenated and compared with concatenated sequences of these regions in other strains. Phylogenetic analysis of the isolates was also performed using three different and widely used methods—Maximum Likelihood, Maximum Parsimony, and Bayesian Analysis—to make more accurate inferences about the evolutionary distance between isolates.

A 1795-nucleotide concatenated sequence from corrected sequences of *gyrB*, *infB*, and *atpD* regions was created for the *B. nigrifluens* group isolates, and a 2439-nucleotide concatenated sequence from corrected sequences of *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* regions was created for the *Brenneria*-like group isolates. The concatenated sequences created for each isolate group were aligned with other genera

closely related to the families of *B. nigrifluens* and *G. quercinecans*. The aligned sequences were analyzed using the ModelFinder tool in Phylosuite v1.2.2 software, and based on the lowest obtained AIC, Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian phylogenetic analysis models were selected, which were GTR+F+R7 and GTR+G4 for the *B. nigrifluens* group, and TIM3e+R6 and SYM+I+G4 for the *Brenneria*-like group, respectively.

The concatenated sequence constructed from *gyrB*, *infB*, and *atpD* regions for the *B. nigrifluens* group isolates showed 100% affiliation of these isolates with known *B. nigrifluens* species in all three phylogenetic methods, and it can be definitively stated that these isolates are *B. nigrifluens*. Additionally, they showed 100% and 99% similarity with each other in Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony methods, respectively, and the posterior probability of these isolates clustering together in the Bayesian method was 97% (Figure 4-18).

The concatenated sequence constructed from *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* regions for the *Brenneria*-like group isolates showed 100% and 92% affiliation of these isolates with *G. quercinecans* strains in Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony methods, respectively, and the posterior probability in the Bayesian method for placement alongside the mentioned strains was 100%. However, the affiliation of these isolates with different strains of this species varied, and they were placed into three groups. The first group included isolates SF67 (Fars), SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), which showed 100% and 58% similarity in Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony methods, respectively, with the parent cluster comprising strains *G. quercinecans* BH 1/65b, *G. quercinecans* N78, *G. quercinecans* LMG 25501, and *G. quercinecans* LMG 25502. The posterior probability of these isolates in the Bayesian method for placement alongside the cluster containing the mentioned strains was 58%. The second group included isolates SF72 and SF74 (Isfahan), whose cluster showed 99% and 72% similarity in Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony, respectively, and a posterior probability of 77% with strain *G. quercinecans* BW 2/28. The third group, which included isolates SF67 (Fars) and SF76 (Isfahan), was placed in a separate cluster with 99% and 50% similarity in Maximum Likelihood and Maximum Parsimony, respectively, and with a posterior probability of 35% alongside strain *G. quercinecans* BER 12 (Figure 4-19).

To compare the *G. quercinecans* isolates obtained in this study with those from previous studies conducted in Iran regarding this specific species, sequences of amplified *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* regions from previous studies were extracted from the NCBI database and aligned with sequences of similar regions from isolates obtained in this study. Sequences of the mentioned regions were only available in studies by Allahverdipour et al. (2021) and Basavand et al. (2021). These sequences, after alignment according to the methods described, were corrected and concatenated. A Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of constructed concatenated sequences was drawn with the TNe+R3 model and 1000 bootstrap replicates (Figure 4-20). The results indicated differences between the studied isolates and those from other studies conducted in Iran, and these isolates were placed at different evolutionary distances compared to isolates from other studies.

Figure 4-18 Combined phylogenetic tree drawn from concatenated housekeeping genes (1795 nucleotides) *gyrB*, *infB*, and *atpD* for *Brenneria nigrifluens* group isolates, with transfer of Maximum Parsimony bootstrap values (middle) and Bayesian posterior probability (right) to the Maximum Likelihood tree (left)

Figure 4-19 Combined phylogenetic tree drawn from concatenated housekeeping genes (2439 nucleotides) *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates, with transfer of Maximum Parsimony bootstrap values (middle) and Bayesian posterior probability (right) to the Maximum Likelihood tree (left)

Figure 4-20 Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree drawn from concatenated housekeeping genes (2439 nucleotides) *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates compared with other studies conducted in Iran and the study by Brady et al. (2014)

4-9-8 Analysis of Concatenated Amino Acid Sequences

The results from nucleotide sequencing indicated diversity among the studied isolates. Although nucleotide differences may increase the probability of mutation in a particular isolate, these differences will not necessarily lead to changes, as there is a high probability that changing one nucleotide will not change its corresponding amino acid. The main reason for this is the existence of 64 codons and only 20 standard amino acids (plus the stop codon) (Osawa and Jukes, 1989). Therefore, generally, the probability that a nucleotide change will not result in a change in the protein (except for a slight difference in translation speed) is approximately 1 in 3. Furthermore, most amino acids are encoded by multiple different codons that differ only in the third base; therefore, if a mutation occurs in the third base, there is a high probability that the resulting codon will still encode the same amino acid, and no change in protein structure will occur.

Thus, even if amino acid substitutions occur, it is possible that the new amino acid is similar to the previous amino acid in terms of chemical properties and has little effect on the structure and function of the protein. However, if the mutation leads to the conversion of an amino acid to a stop codon, the protein function is likely to be disrupted. Therefore, to investigate whether the observed nucleotide differences in the studied isolates have created any specific significance, the amino acid sequences derived from the translation of nucleotide sequences were compared, showing that the *Brenneria*-like group isolates did not differ much from *G. quercinecans*, but the *B. nigrifluens* isolates were somewhat different. As expected, and as previously noted by Falahi Charkhabi et al. (2010), they were

heterogeneous, while they were previously known as homogeneous. Therefore, it appears that the genomic structure of Iranian isolates differs from non-Iranian isolates. Additionally, since walnut is native to Iran and Iranian genotypes are naturally different, it is possible that alongside the Iranian plant genotype, the bacterium *B. nigrifluens* has also evolved.

What has happened with *B. nigrifluens* in Iranian isolates also applies to *G. quercinecans*. The phylogenetic tree drawn based on nucleotide sequences showed that isolates belonging to the *G. quercinecans* group are different from each other, and there is diversity in these isolates, as they were placed at various distances from each other and from other British and Spanish species.

It is generally recommended to use both nucleotide sequence-based and amino acid sequence-based phylogenetic methods for taxonomic inference, as both have their advantages and disadvantages. Synonymous mutations along the nucleotide sequence may not lead to translation and changes in amino acid sequence; however, they provide more evolutionary information compared to amino acid sequences for examining closely related isolates. But analyzing DNA data under nucleotide models has a major computational advantage over analyzing protein data, in that it allows the potential to use advanced models that exist for site-to-site heterogeneity and lineage-to-lineage heterogeneity in the nucleotide substitution process, enabling deeper inference of phylogenetic trees (Kapli et al., 2023).

Therefore, the multi-locus sequencing performed for the two groups, *B. nigrifluens* and *Brenneria*-like, based on nucleotide sequences of protein-coding genes, was also compared. To investigate whether these nucleotide changes have also led to different amino acid translations from each other, amino acid translations of amplified regions in these isolates were performed and concatenated, and compared with the concatenated amino acid translations resulting from the translation of nucleotide sequences of the same regions in other strains. This translation was performed based on codon translation table 11, which is specific to bacteria, archaea, and plastids (plant plastids).

The resulting concatenated amino acid sequence for the *B. nigrifluens* group was 598 amino acids, and for the *Brenneria*-like group, it was 812 amino acids. A phylogenetic tree based on the Maximum Likelihood method was drawn for both groups of isolates, *B. nigrifluens* and *Brenneria*-like, showing 98.2% affiliation of the cluster containing the *B. nigrifluens* group isolates with the cluster containing standard *B. nigrifluens* strains (Figure 4-21). However, as the phylogenetic tree shows, there were differences among the *B. nigrifluens* group isolates with each other and with standard *B. nigrifluens* strains, and there was variable bootstrap percentage among the compared isolates, which increases the probability of diversity among these isolates. But for the *Brenneria*-like group, this result was noteworthy; because although these group isolates had shown differences in nucleotide comparison, here they were placed alongside each other with high similarity (over 99%) and in the cluster containing reference *G. quercinecans* isolates (Figure 4-22).

Therefore, based on the obtained results and comparison with current data, it can be said that isolates SF82, SF81, SF80, SF79, SF78, SF77 (Isfahan), SF59 (Fars) are definitively *B. nigrifluens*, and isolates SF67 (Fars), SF18, SF29, SF30, SF31, SF34, SF41 (Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad), SF72, SF74, and SF76 (Isfahan) are *G. quercinecans*.

Figure 4-21 Concatenated phylogenetic tree created (598 amino acids) from the connection of amino acid translations of protein-coding sequences *gyrB*, *infB*, and *atpD* for *Brenneria nigrifluens* group isolates

Figure 4-22 Concatenated phylogenetic tree created (812 amino acids) from the connection of amino acid translations of protein-coding sequences *gyrB*, *rpoB*, *infB*, and *atpD* for *Brenneria*-like group isolates

4-10 Bacterial Canker: The Necessity of Continuous Monitoring and Control

Walnut cultivation is an important industry in Iran, providing vital income for many farmers. However, bacterial canker disease caused by *B. nigrifluens* severely affects the quality and quantity of walnut fruit production, leading to economic damage. Given that Iran is one of the world's largest producers and exporters of walnuts, the management of this disease is essential for maintaining the quality and reputation of Iranian walnuts (FAO, 2021). Iranian walnut cultivation is primarily concentrated in the hills and elevated regions of the Zagros and Alborz Mountain ranges. Provinces such as Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, Isfahan, and Fars are renowned for their Iranian walnut production, areas which were also historically known for their abundant oak tree vegetation.

Bacterial canker has been observed in recent years on Iranian walnuts, various oak species, and ornamental trees worldwide, showing symptoms such as irregular stem lesions, bark cracks, and dark exudates from wounds, similar to symptoms described for diseases caused by several *Brenneria* species. In recent decades, *B. nigrifluens* has been the primary agent of these symptoms in Iran (Roshangar and Harighi, 2009; Falahi Charkhabi et al., 2010; Khodaygan and Habibi, 2019). Recently, however, *G. quercinecans* and *Brenneria rosea* sp. *rosea* have been identified as new causal agents of bleeding canker disease on walnut trees (Allahverdipour et al., 2020). This pathogen has previously caused oak decline in various parts of the world. In recent years, new reports have associated *G. quercinecans* as a primary or co-occurring agent of bacterial canker in oak forests in Lithuania, Poland, and Switzerland (Ruffner et al., 2020; Tkaczyk et al., 2021; Zalkalns and Celma, 2021). Based on laboratory data, *G. quercinecans* can survive in rainwater for approximately 3 months and in forest soil for up to 28 days (Pettifor et al., 2020). This demonstrates the ecological widespread distribution of this agent and its ability to expand its host range, thus it should be considered an important opportunistic pathogen. Reports of this bacterium on various hosts including walnut and forest trees confirm that this agent can act as an independent pathogen alongside *Brenneria* species, which are recognized as the main agents of bacterial canker in walnut trees in Iran, causing damage to these valuable plants. Therefore, more precise and extensive studies are needed to investigate the presence of *G. quercinecans* in different regions or on new hosts as a pathogen or associated agent, to fully characterize its genetic properties and develop control strategies against outbreaks.

Isfahan, Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad, and Fars provinces are considered key walnut cultivation areas in Iran, but studies in these provinces have been limited. Additionally, these regions are recognized as habitats for many native oak species in Iran. Therefore, this study was conducted to investigate and identify other primary and dominant agents associated with walnut bacterial canker alongside *B. nigrifluens* in these provinces and to examine their phenotypic and molecular characteristics, as the first step for preventing and controlling a disease is its accurate identification.

Of the 100 samples collected from symptomatic trees, only 21 isolates out of 80 were able to induce necrotic symptoms on immature walnut fruits and 5-year-old walnut seedling branches, indicating that 74% of the initially isolated samples lacked pathogenicity. However, these non-pathogenic isolates cannot be overlooked. In recent years, reports of non-pathogenic bacteria associated with pathogenic bacteria have increased in various studies, demonstrating the co-evolution of host and pathogen in relation to each other. This is because non-pathogenic isolates may have either developed symbiotic capabilities with the plant over time or lost their pathogenicity-related structures (Kube et al., 2008; Martins et al., 2020). This endless cycle of compatibility and incompatibility between pathogenic bacteria and plants has been the driving force behind species evolution for millions of years. Plants have developed various defense mechanisms against bacteria, while bacteria have evolved new pathogenicity strategies to overcome these novel defensive methods. One of the most interesting examples of the complexity of this arms race is the bacterium *Pseudomonas syringae*, which uses a Type Three Secretion System (T3SS) to penetrate plant cells and, by injecting effector proteins, manipulates the host's normal metabolic functions, allowing bacterial colonization in plant tissue (Büttner, 2012). In response, plants such as *Arabidopsis thaliana* have developed resistance genes that can specifically recognize some of these bacterial effectors and initiate immune responses to prevent bacterial infection (Block et al., 2010). However, the ongoing competition leads to a continuous cycle of compatibility and incompatibility, as some strains of *P. syringae* have also been able to develop novel effectors that prevent their recognition by some plant resistance genes (Jones and Dangl, 2006).

Martins et al. (2020) recently identified a new species of *Xanthomonas* from symptomatic leaves and even asymptomatic buds of ornamental walnuts, including both pathogenic and non-pathogenic isolates. Interestingly, these isolates with differing pathogenicity capabilities were both obtained from the same tree, which demonstrates the co-evolution of pathogen and host, as both pathogens and non-pathogens can exist in a single host. The study showed that non-pathogenic and pathogenic isolates share more

than 98 percent similarity based on multilocus sequence typing and DNA-DNA hybridization, but one isolate causes disease in walnut leaves while the other is non-pathogenic. Genomic analysis revealed that the pathogenic isolate possesses a complete Type Three Secretion System (T3SS) and several Type Three effector proteins, whereas the non-pathogenic isolate lacks most genes related to this system.

This continuous compatibility and incompatibility highlight the remarkable adaptability of pathogens and hosts. Furthermore, the absence of suitable environmental conditions or specific hosts during the sampling period can affect their ability to manifest symptoms (Brader et al., 2017). Therefore, it is essential to evaluate and monitor the potential of non-pathogenic isolates associated with pathogenic isolates.

The growing risk of diseases caused by new and unknown aggressive pathogens or the pathogenicity of previously known opportunistic bacterial isolates due to climate change and environmental factors necessitates more precise and extensive studies of pathogenic bacteria in relation to their distribution and symbiosis with new hosts (Janda and Abbott, 2021). For example, in Spain and Japan, two new species named *Erwinia piriflorinigrans* and *E. uzenensis* were discovered in the genus *Erwinia*, initially thought to belong to *Erwinia amylovora* due to their similarities. However, further analyses, examination of their molecular characteristics, and DNA-DNA hybridization confirmed that these species are indeed new and unique (Lopez et al., 2021; Matsuura et al., 2012).

In this study, the number of samples found from oak trees was lower than infected walnut samples, with only 16 samples collected from symptomatic oak trees in the studied areas. One reason for this decrease is the particular reduction of oak trees in recent years in the Zagros regions. These trees, which once covered a vast expanse of forest in these areas, have now significantly decreased due to various reasons over the past two decades. Decreased rainfall, increased temperatures, and longer dry seasons are among the most important reasons for oak decline. Additionally, infections with various fungi and bacteria have contributed to the decline of Iranian oak (*Q. brantii*). For example, the bacteria *B. goodwinii* and *G. quercinecans* are plant pathogens considered among the most important factors in oak decline in English forests, which have recently been reported in Iran as well (Bakhshi ganje et al., 2020; Zolfaghari et al., 2022). Notably, the survival rate of *G. quercinecans* in forest soils is much higher compared to *B. goodwinii*. According to laboratory data from Pettifor et al. (2020), *G. quercinecans* can survive in rainwater and forest soil for approximately 3 months and 28 days, respectively, indicating its ability for widespread ecological distribution, host-jumping to various hosts, and transformation into an opportunistic and dangerous pathogen. Reports of this bacterium from various forest and ornamental tree hosts in Iran in recent years indicate that this agent can cause disease in important plants of this ecosystem either alone or in association with various species of the genus *Brenneria*. As demonstrated in this study, a significant portion of the isolated strains, contrary to previous predictions, belong to the species *G. quercinecans*. Another finding in this thesis was the pathogenicity of the oak pathogenic isolate (SF67) of this species on walnut, which itself warns of this bacterium's high capability, given its high persistence in forest soils, to expand its host range. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct more studies on its emergence and presence in other hosts and forest regions of Iran before this agent becomes an uncontrollable pathogen, to prevent a potential damaging outbreak, as host-shifting in bacteria is very common and their host range often overlaps rather than forming distinct pathotypes (Morris and Moury, 2019).

One of the most important methods for preventing and controlling plant diseases is the availability of reliable, referenceable, and accessible data for everyone. However, one of the challenges faced during this research, which still persists, is the lack of a unified center in the country for maintaining bacterial pathogen isolates, which limits further and more extensive studies related to the pathogenicity of these agents. This is because these isolates have either been maintained over many years or have become contaminated, or they no longer exist, or if they do exist, significant budget has not been allocated to them, or the necessary collaboration from the country's researchers with these institutions does not take

place. For example, nearly 30 years have passed since the first report of *B. nigrifluens* in Iran (Rahimian, 1989), and it has been reported in different parts of the country since then. However, comparable molecular studies to examine the similarities or differences between these isolates have not been conducted, or if they have, they have been limited to a few regions, or these isolates are no longer available. This situation has resulted in disease control focusing more on the elimination of these plants rather than on preventing outbreaks.

Chapter Five

General Conclusion and Recommendations

5-1 General Conclusion

The results obtained from multilocus sequence analysis showed that although *Brenneria nigrifluens* is still isolated from walnut trees in central regions of Iran, the prevalence of *Gibbsiella quercinecans* has also increased in these areas. Considering that these regions are the natural habitat of oak trees, which are the primary host of the aforementioned bacterium, there is a possibility of host-jumping from these plants to other important plants such as walnut and other nut trees.

5-2 Recommendations

1. Investigation of the host range of *G. quercinecans* in other forest hosts
2. Definition of a new pathosystem, examination of *G. quercinecans* and *B. nigrifluens* isolates in oak hosts
3. Examination of isolates associated with bacterial canker symptoms
4. Investigation of synergistic and antagonistic effects of isolates in walnut and oak hosts

Appendices

1. **Gelatin Hydrolysis Test Reagent**

12 grams of mercury chloride dissolved in 16 milliliters of concentrated hydrochloric acid, and the volume is brought to 100 milliliters with distilled water. The solution is stored in a dark, tightly closed bottle at room temperature.

2. **Lugol's Reagent**

The solution contains 2 grams of potassium iodide, 1 gram of iodine in 300 milliliters of sterile distilled water, and after overnight storage at room temperature, it is filtered with filter paper and stored in a dark bottle with a tightly closed lid at room temperature.

3. **Esculin Hydrolysis Test Medium**

The culture medium containing 1 percent esculin, 0.05 percent ferric citrate, 1 percent peptone, and 15 gr Agar in one liter of distilled water was dissolved and autoclaved.

4. **YS Culture Medium**

Culture medium containing 0.05 percent ammonium phosphate, 0.05 percent dipotassium phosphate, 0.02 percent magnesium sulfate, 0.05 percent sodium chloride, and 0.5 percent yeast extract in 1 liter of distilled water was dissolved and autoclaved.

5. **Urease Culture Medium**

Culture medium containing 1 gram of yeast extract, 0.5 gram of ammonium phosphate, 0.5 gram of dipotassium phosphate, 0.2 gram of magnesium sulfate, 5 grams of sodium chloride dissolved in 1 liter of water, and 0.001 gram of cresol red is added to the medium as an indicator. After sterilizing the medium under autoclave conditions, 40 grams of urea is dissolved in 200 milliliters of distilled water, sterilized using a Millipore filter, and added to 1 liter of the above medium.

6. **Thornley Culture Medium**

Culture medium containing 1 gram of peptone, 5 grams of table salt, 0.3 gram percent of dipotassium phosphate, 10 grams of arginine, 3 grams of agar, and 0.01 gram of phenol red dissolved in 1 liter of distilled water. The pH of the medium was adjusted to approximately 7.2, divided into test tubes, and autoclaved.

7. **Ayer Culture Medium**

Ayer base medium including 0.1 percent ammonium dihydrogen phosphate, 0.02 percent potassium chloride, 0.02 percent magnesium sulfate heptahydrate, and 1.2 percent agarose along with bromothymol blue dye was added and autoclaved. Sugars and amino acids were added to the autoclaved Ayer medium by tyndallization (boiling for 25 minutes on 3 consecutive days) and distributed in sterile petri dishes.

8. **CTAB Buffer**

CTAB buffer was prepared to a volume of 100 milliliters. 2 grams of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, 1.4 molar sodium chloride, 20 millimolar ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and 100 millimolar Tris hydrochloride were brought to a volume of 100 milliliters with distilled water. The pH of the buffer was adjusted to 8.

9. **TBE Buffer**

10. TBE buffer containing 10.8 grams of Tris base (hydroxymethyl aminomethane), 5.5 grams of boric acid, and 4 grams of 0.5 molar ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) was brought to a volume of 100 milliliters. The pH of the buffer was adjusted to 8.

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